

BEST PRACTICES OF OUTSTANDING SCHOOL PAPER ADVISER: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Best Practices of Outstanding School Paper Adviser: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

This multiple case study aimed to accumulate and understand the best practices of school paper adviser. Using a purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating six (6) school paper advisers were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: recognizing and motivating students to development, prioritizing open communication, encountering challenges in generating interest and recruiting members; and minimizing adviser influence on student work. In response to how advisers overcome challenges in managing the school paper organization, the following themes were being extracted; commitment to continuous professional growth for effective journalism advising, balancing workload, practicing effective resource management; and fostering students development in journalism by enhancing skill. Upon reflecting to their practices and experiences, they arrived at the following insights: connecting to broader trends, showcasing school achievements, encouraging student participation in campus journalism. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *practices, school paper adviser, multiple-case approach, qualitative, cross-case analysis*

Introduction

School papers, sometimes called campus papers or publications, have been a fixture in many schools worldwide for many decades. It serves as an avenue or medium for students to express their thoughts and practice their journalistic skills. On the other hand, the adviser plays a great role in the success of a school paper. The press conference held by the institution is considered a primary source of information that influences opinions and directs personal behavior. Schools Press Conference is a Department of Education (DepEd)-sponsored campus media competition with numerous facets (Paguirigan et al., 2023).

In a global setting, specifically at Indiana University in Estados Unidos, it was revealed that even before the onset of the pandemic, there were factors that hindered the success of campus publications and highlighted the obstacles school paper advisers, such as lack of financial resources, limited curriculum integration, and inadequate teacher training on campus paper organization advising. This lack of formal education in journalistic practices means that many students enter the school paper with little to no training, making it challenging to meet professional standards. The success of campus publications relies heavily on their publication advisers, who undertake a range of responsibilities, including providing editorial guidance, fostering skill development, and maintaining journalistic standards (Burelison et al., 2021).

In the Philippines, specifically at Abuyog Community College in Leyte, the campus publication was often undervalued compared to other academic disciplines, leading to reduced support and funding. While these advisors had to face several challenges and issues that impacted the effective implementation of the program, another unexpected challenge took place– the pandemic. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted traditional educational paradigms and campus dynamics in unprecedented ways. This led to the adjustment to the virtual setting with limited face-to-face interaction. This also allowed campus advisors' roles to transition virtually, which posed various challenges and profound opportunities. In ensuring the success of campus publications, publication advisers play a crucial role in guiding and supporting student journalists and their publications within educational institutions. Their responsibilities encompass various aspects of journalism, mentorship, and education (Advincula & Adtoon, 2024).

This current study of school papers from the advisers' perspective is timely due to the changing norms in journalism. Printed media, such as newspapers and magazines, are at risk of losing their importance because of the rapid growth of the internet, where almost everything has become digitalized. As such, students appear to be losing interest in participating or supporting school papers. Thus, this study can be relevant in making the students, teachers, and school administrators realize that the school paper is a significant factor in developing media awareness and literacy among the students.

Furthermore, this issue has not been adequately addressed. Although there are few studies conducted in the context of school journalism, like the study of Calub (2023) entitled, "Campus Journalism and Challenges Faced by Student Journalist," which examines the challenges and responsibilities of student journalists in writing and reporting, and Reinjoe et al.'s (2022) research, "Paperless Publication: Surveying the Shift of Campus Journalism" which explored the transition from traditional to digital journalism, there remains a gap in literature. Another recent study in the Philippines explores school paper advisers' preparedness and coaching styles. The study of Deloria et al. (2024) entitled "Preparedness and Coaching Styles of the School Paper Advisers on Campus Journalism in the New Normal". The study focused on school paper advisers' level of preparedness and coaching styles, considering their background knowledge, training, availability of resources, and facilitated learning. However, this current study will fill that void as there is little to no literature about school papers from the advisers' perspective. By so, his study utilized solely qualitative research methods, and the respondents were only the school paper advisers.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to explore the stories of experience, practices, and insights of school paper advisers, and this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What unique strategies do successful school paper adviser employ to foster a thriving environment for journalism within their educational institution?
2. What are the lived experiences of advisers in managing school papers?
3. How do advisers cope with the challenges they faced with regard to handling school paper organization?
4. What insights can the advisers share that may be helpful to other school paper advisers and school administrative?

Methodology

Research Design

The multiple-case qualitative research design was used as an approach. This research strategy was utilized since it permitted the researcher to attain the study's goals, which were to comprehend and investigate the pedagogical practices of mathematics teachers. According to Rashid et al. (2019), qualitative multiple-case studies offer a descriptive analysis of a particular occurrence in a given environment. Furthermore, this research design illustrated a procedural effort to determine the phenomena's experiences, perspectives, insights, observable particular context, and observable specific context through interviews and interactive discussions (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

This study's qualitative research design was considered the most appropriate because it allowed the researcher to delve into the information gathered about the best practices of school paper advisers. A qualitative design was used to identify and comprehend distinct cases, statements, and descriptions of their experiences and insights. Purposive sampling was used in this study to recruit participants and informants. Thematic analysis was also used to analyze the research data collection. In addition, trustworthiness was used in this study to provide confidence in the data collection. Similarly, ethical considerations were considered to ensure that the study was carried out while protecting the human participants' welfare.

Meanwhile, a case study was also defined as an in-depth, systematic assessment of a single person, group, community, or other entity in which the researcher investigated detailed data about multiple variables. In addition, it offered a deeper understanding of the instances as a whole by analyzing the similarities and differences of the individual cases within the quintain (Heale & Twycross, 2017). Nevertheless, it was essential to recognize that conducting numerous case studies had advantages and disadvantages. Multiple case study implementation could be expensive and time-consuming (Gustafsson, 2017).

In this study, multiple-case study was commonly employed in social sciences and behavioral studies to extract a single set of insights from complex contexts. Consequently, it enabled the researcher to investigate various facets of the phenomenon, determine the relationship, and comprehend the process of the entire environment holistically in order to reach a conclusion. The researcher believed that this methodology was appropriate for the study because a multiple-case study took into consideration the experiences, difficulties, efforts, sacrifices, and insights of school paper advisers. Using multiple case studies, the researcher obtained a comprehensive understanding of the best practices of school paper advisers when managing school papers. In addition, a thematic analysis was used to generate subtopics for interpretation when analyzing the data. In addition to random sampling, purposeful sampling was used to determine who was eligible to participate in the study. By considering various ethical responsibilities, this research maintained the integrity of the collected data's truthfulness.

Participants

The study participants were the school paper advisers from different high schools in Davao del Norte. Six (6) participants from different high schools in Davao del Norte were selected based on the criteria of the study. All six (6) participants underwent in-depth interviews, each individually interviewed by the researcher.

This number was determined following Creswell (2013), who determined that the optimal number of participants in a qualitative study ranged from three (3) to fifteen (15). Data saturation was obtained during the data collection process by including this group of participants in a qualitative research study.

During the selection of participants, a non-probability sampling technique known as purposeful sampling was utilized. Purposive sampling, or judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, was founded on the researcher's discretion in selecting the units to be studied (e.g., individuals, cases/organizations, or data points). The investigated sample size was typically quite small compared to probability sampling techniques. It was a type of non-probability sampling in which the researcher decided which individuals to include in the sample based on various criteria, such as expert knowledge of the research topic or capacity and inclination to participate in the study (Rai, 2016).

The criteria for selecting the participants were as follows: the participant must be a teacher from a high school within Davao del Norte; they have sufficient experience in handling or managing school papers; and they must be a school paper adviser. The following were

the specified criteria for participants and informants in each case.

Case 1 of this study includes two teachers from Kapalong National High School; they must be school paper advisers and have sufficient experience handling school papers.

Case 2 of this study includes two teachers from Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School; they must be school paper advisers and have sufficient experience handling school papers.

Case 3 of this study includes two teachers from Sto Niño National High School; they must be school paper advisers and have sufficient experience handling school papers.

Procedure

When conducting the study, the researcher adhered to a rigorous protocol. This data collection method included everything from the pre-interview to the post-interview phases. Then, the researcher developed interview guide questions and ensured the panel of validators validated the interview guide questions. The researcher then received an endorsement letter. The researcher requested consent from the adviser to conduct the study using the endorsement paper. Following that, the researcher sought authorization from the KCAST College President's Office, requesting a letter allowing the researcher to conduct a face-to-face interview with the School Paper advisors.

Upon approval, the researcher obtained a letter seeking authorization to participate in the study for the selected subjects. Once the chosen individuals agreed to participate in the study, the researcher gave them a consent form to sign. The researcher then investigated after receiving authorization from the commission. The researchers offered an orientation for all participants prior to the interview. During the orientation, the researcher explained the goal of the study, the methodology, and the rights of the interview participants. In addition, the researcher requested permission to videotape the entire interview. Finally, after the interview, the researcher ensured the secrecy of all recorded interviews. The researcher transcribed the captured data. The participants checked the transcribed data. After the data was verified, the researcher translated and analyzed it. The data analysis findings were utilized to form conclusions and offer recommendations.

Data Analysis

The data gathered during the in-depth interviews were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The procedures were taken in accordance with Creswell's (2009) recommended data analysis process.

The translated responses of the participants were coded to construct a thematic analysis of the data for this case study. Thematic analysis, often known as coding, was the process of categorizing responses or recognizing repeating themes in a text to construct a thematic concept structure. These prominent themes provided valuable data insights that could be quantified. Using the rigorous process of thematic analysis, a data set could be sorted into themes or patterns. This enabled the researcher to identify and generate themes from the collected data (Dye, 2021).

The researcher based his or her data analysis on the transcripts and translations of the informants' responses. When theming, the researcher used the coding process to categorize and arrange the repeated responses to develop and construct a theme analysis with the help of the data analyst. The linkages, parallels, and oppositions between the concepts were used to categorize and assess them.

Ethical Considerations

Scientists and researchers must always follow ethical principles when collecting data from persons. These principles serve as a guide for research designs and processes. Understanding real-world events, discovering effective medicines, studying behavior, and improving people's lives are typically the goals of human research. When conducting research, ethical norms must be followed. These characteristics maintain academic or scientific integrity, promote the validity of research, and protect study participants' rights (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for person is an ethical value that deals with accepting the autonomy of study participants. The principle of autonomy can be protected by giving participants with clear and understandable information about the research project in the participants' information booklet, hence improving their informed consent (Kalu & Bwalya, 2017).

In this study, the researcher created information consent forms for the subjects. The letters were sent to everyone interested in the study's progress. This was done as a service to those who contributed to the research. Everyone who wanted to participate in this study was given the chance. During the interviews, the researcher respected the viewpoints of the participants. To earn the participants' respect, the researcher first respected the topic. Individuals needed to consider their point of view, culture, way of life, and decision to participate or not participate in the interview. Participants were always respected because they were more important than the study. Additionally, the researcher informed the participants that they had the right to be informed of the study results.

Consent was designed to aid in creating trustworthy and honest research collaborations and defend people's right to refuse to engage in research. A critical criterion for consent's validity is that an individual's decision is voluntary and based on clear, unambiguous information about what participation in the research will entail (Klykken, 2021)

This study invited participants to make educated judgments and engage voluntarily. The researcher ensured that all participants were excited about the project and eager to participate. When gathering data and information, it was also necessary to obtain authorization from study participants to record their responses and share their experiences. Furthermore, the participants were informed that they had the right to ask questions during the interview, declined to answer sensitive questions, and left the session without explanation. If participants left during the interview, the researcher respected their decision not to complete it.

Beneficence refers to the researcher's responsibility to protect the safety of study participants at all times. This concept has been given two maxims: "do not harm" and "do everything in one's ability to maximize benefits while limiting damage" (Farrugia, 2019).

The community and participants benefited from this study because the findings could be used to improve the best practices of school paper advisers and inspire them to develop effective management of school papers and strategies that would aid fellow school paper advisers in handling school papers and raise the standard of school paper of education in the neighborhood.

To protect the safety of all participants, the researcher found a secure venue where the participants and researchers could conduct a face-to-face interview. Participants in the interview process were given the opportunity to relate their stories in a safe environment where they did not face rejection or judgment. There were no unattended or unsecured information files, and all participants were always protected. Data were kept safe and secure to avoid psychological risks such as shame, embarrassment, and other negative outcomes. The research ensured that the risk of COVID-19 transmission between the interviewer and participants was avoided by following safety protocols during the interview. There was no direct advantage of the interview in terms of what the study provided for participants.

Confidentiality refers to a researcher's responsibility to protect the information entrusted to them. If other stakeholders can identify participants, a breach of secrecy may have catastrophic consequences. Establishing trusting relationships with participants is also essential (Tremblay & Cadieux, 2018). In addition, confidentiality will be preserved in this study through password-protected files and data storage. This is also consistent with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

To preserve the participants' privacy, the researcher disguised their identities, such as their names and addresses, before providing personal information about them. The researcher substituted the participants' names with pseudonyms. Names and other identifying information about participants may have been retained in separate, secure files. The researcher deleted identifiers in order to obtain "clean" data. A clean data collection contained no information that could be used to identify respondents, such as their name or address (such identifying information may have been maintained elsewhere, in separate, secure files). Data were stored and deleted three years after the study was accomplished. Specific identifiers were easy to recognize and handle.

Justice is defined as treating all individuals equally, which means that everyone has an equal opportunity to share the benefits and expenses of the research regardless of their age, gender, race, religion, or socioeconomic level, among other variables. Yet, it is the researcher's ethical responsibility to guarantee that her research does not result in unfairness or prejudice at any point in the process, especially in selecting research participants, so that no group is excluded (Farrugia, 2019).

Every participant's participation in the research was acknowledged. Throughout the investigation, the researcher gave appropriate tokens to study participants to thank them and appreciate their efforts in the study. In addition, the researcher used purposive sampling to properly select interview participants and informants based on a set of inclusion criteria that were appropriate for the study.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into three sections. Part one focused on the data collected from participants, from which the qualitative data were derived. Part two reviews the data analysis procedures and steps in categorizing the emergent themes from the in-depth interviews (IDI) for each case. Part three summarized the responses obtained during the data collection process.

Participants

The study's participants were school paper advisers in high school, as shown in Table 1 in this chapter. The participants were all school teachers, so the researcher had faith in them to provide the information needed for this study.

The interview was conducted via audio recording and took place outside the campus. The researcher asked the participants if they wanted to be interviewed. I got what I wanted, and both parties, the interviewer and the interviewee, were pleased with the outcome, which resulted in a smooth flow and open communication whenever additional or probing questions were required. Participants could decline to answer any question they deemed unprofitable or against their will. To ensure confidentiality, the data gathered during the interviews was kept in the strictest of secrecy, and only the researcher and the informants had access to such information that was voiced but not included due to the nature of the study.

To conform to the data collection process, the researcher used his smartphone to record the participants' responses to the session proceedings. The researcher also asked all the respondents if he could take videos or record the entire conversation while the interviews were taking place, and they all agreed politely. They all accommodated the request and understood it except for one: that their identities be kept anonymous in the study Boyce and Neale (2006).

All participants in each case were given pseudonyms in order to protect their identities. In case 1, Buttercup is not her real name. The researcher gave her this pseudonym because, during the interview, she was very active and energetic in answering the questions; she resembles Buttercup. Her voice during the interview was calm and had a good tone. On the other hand, Sharp is not his real name. The researcher gave this pseudonym because, during the interview, he answered the questions directly to the point as much as possible; his intent and idea were clear and concise, which is why the researcher called him Sharp.

In case 2, pseudonyms were also given to each participant to protect their identities. Brainy is not his real name. The researcher gave this name to him because, during the interview, the interviewer noticed that he was smart and witty. Calm, also not her real name; thus, the researcher gave her this pseudonym because, during the interview, the researcher noticed that she was calm in answering the question.

Lastly, in case 3, pseudonyms were also given to the participants of the study as well. The researcher describes Bubbly as cheerful and optimistic; during the interview, Bubbly shares a lot about herself. That is why the researcher calls her Bubbly. On the other hand, Happy is not her real name because the researcher noticed her during the interview, and the participant answered the question happily.

Categorization of Data

After completing in-depth interviews, the voice-recorded exchanges were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The researcher began the analysis with the coding process.

Coding organizes materials into chunks of text segments before giving meaning to information. The coding process was used to describe the people's settings and the categories of themes for analysis. These themes were used to shape the overall description of the phenomenon under investigation.

The themes were presented by the research question and referred to as major themes in order to categorize the data. The study's themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated to provide a vivid description. Then came the conclusion and verification, the point in the study where the preliminary ideas and patterns about the findings are developed (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>Cases</i>	<i>Pseudonym</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Code</i>
SNNHS	Buttercup	Female	High School Teacher	IDI-01
	Sharp	Male	High School Teacher	IDI-02
BNVNHS	Brainy	Male	High School Teacher	IDI-03
	Calm	Female	High School Teacher	IDI-04
KNHS	Bubbly	Female	High School Teacher	IDI-05
	Happy	Female	High School Teacher	IDI-06

In order to add credibility to the research, the researcher took note of the construct's credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. Member checking was performed in addition to the triangulation technique to address credibility. This was accomplished by providing participants with a copy of the interview transcript so that they could provide feedback and attest to its authenticity. So far, no informant has disputed the transcript or provided feedback to the contrary. They all responded positively by signing the participant's verification form. The triangulation was achieved because the study included more than two sources, namely readings from related literature and participants (Guba & Lincoln, 1985; Creswell & Miller, 2003).

The researcher provided a review trail that was referred to in order to address dependability and confirmability. It was created to allow the research review panel to validate our interpretations, assumptions, and hypotheses (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher made no claim from the start that the findings were generalizable because these perceptions were based solely on the participants' personal experiences in the aforementioned locations. Nonetheless, the researcher agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of qualitative research are ensured, transferability is also addressed (Gempes et al., 2009).

Case 1 – Sto Niño

This case is composed of two participants, one male and one female. All of them are school paper advisers and were selected as the research participants for the study.

Sto Niño National High School is located at Sto Niño Talaingod Davao del Norte, and the school joined various competitions that include school journalism. The Sto Niño National High School is one of the schools that excelled in extracurricular activities and produced a talented student.

These high school teachers are teachers who are school paper advisers. They understand that being a school paper adviser can be a rewarding yet challenging role that requires a mix of skills, dedication, and passion for both journalism and education. Their primary role is to guide and mentor students in producing a school newspaper or magazine. This involves teaching them journalistic principles such as research, interviewing, writing, and editing. School paper advisers also help students understand media ethics and the importance of responsible reporting.

School Paper adviser revealed that being a school paper adviser requires a deep commitment to journalism and education. This role allows you to significantly impact students' lives by nurturing their passion for writing and journalism while helping them develop valuable skills that extend far beyond the newsroom. Advising a school paper can come with challenges, such as balancing academic demands with extracurricular activities, managing conflicts within the team, or dealing with sensitive topics in reporting. Being prepared to handle these challenges with diplomacy and professionalism is essential.

Research Question No. 1: What unique strategies do successful school paper advisers employ to foster a thriving environment for journalism within their educational institutions?

Based on the first question, the researcher found many themes. The following are the themes that have emerged, which the researcher reflected on and analyzed.

Finding Relevance of the Story to the Community

Actively seeking out topics that resonate with local interests, concerns, and achievements, the adviser ensures that the paper becomes a vital communication tool within the school and surrounding area. This approach fosters a deeper connection between the school and its community and educates students on the importance of journalism in reflecting and understanding community dynamics.

It was revealed during the interview that exploring diverse perspectives can enrich the understanding of what constitutes an impactful story. According to Buttercup (pseudonym), considering narratives that resonate deeply with various cultural backgrounds and experiences broadens the scope of what might be significant to different groups. She said:

“We talk about what makes a story important, like if it affects a lot of people or if it's something happening nearby. I also encourage them to look at what is going on in their communities and think about what matters to them and their friends.” (IDI-01)

It was supported by Sharp (pseudonym), who said that encouraging students to adopt a journalistic mindset can empower them to critically analyze and report on immediate school events and broader societal issues impacting their community. He said:

“Train them to stay alert to ongoing school events and broader societal issues, teaching them to look at everyday occurrences through the lens of a journalist.” (IDI-02)

Assisting Students in Idea Generation

Providing guidance on identifying compelling story angles, conducting thorough research, and exploring diverse perspectives, the adviser empowers students to develop stories that resonate with their peers and the broader community. This ensures that the school paper remains dynamic and relevant by continuously generating fresh, engaging content that reflects its readership's evolving interests and concerns.

At this point, the researcher asked the participants how they helped the students formulate ideas. When interviewed, Buttercup (pseudonym) told the researcher that by instilling values early on principles, educators not only prepare students to navigate the complexities of media and communication but also empower them to contribute responsibly to public discourse. She responded:

“Akong gina tabangan akong students na ma excite na mag tell ug stories ug mag ask ug mga question by creating gud ug supportive na environment. Then naga share mi ug ideas para mag connect. We talk about kung unsa gyud ang maging isang journalist and how to be fair and honest.” (IDI-01)

(I help students get excited about telling stories and asking questions by creating a supportive environment. Then we would share our ideas to collect ideas. We talk about what it means to be a journalist and how to be fair and honest.)

Sharp (pseudonym) supported the previous statement that he also implements brainstorming sessions as it will serve as invaluable opportunities for students to refine their storytelling skills and develop their critical thinking abilities. He stated:

“Naa mi regular brainstorming session na gina himo kung asa ang mga students maka tindog sa ilang mga ideas ug maka receive pud ug feedback” (IDI-02)

(Regular brainstorming sessions are held where students can pitch their ideas and receive feedback.)

Building a Foundation for Student Journalism

In the interviews, it was revealed that building a solid foundation for student journalism is a crucial strategy for a school paper adviser, laying the groundwork for professional standards and ethical practices. This involves teaching students the fundamentals of journalism, including fact-checking, source verification, and unbiased reporting. The adviser guides students in understanding the importance of accuracy, fairness, and integrity in their work, instilling a commitment to ethical journalism. Buttercup (pseudonym) articulated that integrating practical skills with ethical considerations is essential in preparing students for the complexities of journalism. She stated:

“I teach them the basics like how to write news stories ug unsaon pud pag interview sa mga tao. Gina storyahan sad namo ang mga important rules like dapat honest ka and respectful. I show them sad unsaon pag gamit sa mga tools like cameras ug computers for

making stories. Ug gina tabangan pud nako sila na mas masabtan pa ang mga laws ug ethics behind journalism arun maka balo sila how to do their job responsibly” (IDI-01).

(I teach them the basics like how to write news stories and Interview people. We also talk about important rules like being honest and respectful. I show them how to use tools like cameras and computers for making stories. And I help them understand the laws and ethics behind journalism, so they know how to do their job responsibly.)

Sharp (pseudonym) also mentioned that establishing a solid foundation in journalism ensures that students understand the field's fundamental principles and responsibilities within it. He shared:

“It is important that the student have a basic foundation in journalism, para pud kabalo ang bata unsa iyang gisudlan unsa iyang role and work.” (IDI-02)

(It is important that the student has a basic foundation in journalism so that the child knows what they are getting into and understands their role and work.)

Fostering Student Interest in Journalism by Enhancing Skill

Creating an environment that encourages curiosity, creativity, and exploration of various journalistic styles and formats. The adviser may organize workshops, guest lectures, and field trips to expose students to different aspects of journalism, from investigative reporting to feature writing. Buttercup (pseudonym) told the researcher that engaging students through interactive and enjoyable activities fosters a deeper connection to journalism. Demonstrating how journalism intersects with their personal interests and everyday experiences, educators inspire a genuine interest in learning more about storytelling and media ethics. She articulated:

“Then naa koy fun activities sama sa kunwari reporters sila or mag practice unsaon mag interview ug tao. By himoong fun ang journalism ug ipakita unsaon pag connect ni sa ilahang mga interest, ma-curious ang bata and mas gusto sila makabalo.” (IDI-01)

(Then, I do fun activities like pretending to be reporters or practicing how to interview someone. By making journalism fun and showing how it connects to their interests, students get curious and want to learn more.)

Sharp (pseudonym) claimed that organizing workshops featuring guest speakers from diverse backgrounds in journalism enriches students' understanding of the field's impact and possibilities. These sessions not only provide insights into different journalistic roles and practices but also highlight real-world examples of how student journalism can drive meaningful change within educational settings and beyond. He shared:

“Organize ug mga workshops with guest speakers nga naa sa field sa journalism ug maghatag ug mga activities and examples kung papaano ang student journalism has effected change sa kada iya-iyang educational settings, kung unsa kini ka lingaw”. (IDI-02)

(Organize workshops with guest speakers from the journalism field and showcase activities and examples of how student journalism has effected change in various educational settings, how fun it is.)

Encouraging Student Independence

Promoting independence for pupils is a unique approach for a school newspaper advisor, enabling students to take charge of their writing pursuits and personal development. By assigning activities like story assignments, editing assignments, and layout design, this method lets students take initiative and solve difficulties on their own. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared that she allows students to select their own stories and make editorial decisions, and educators empower them to explore their interests and perspectives authentically. She said that:

“Gina hayaan nako ang mga bata na mubuhat ug trabaho nga sila lang, pero naa ko didtu para mutabang sa ilaha kung need nila ang akong tabang. Ang paghatag sa ilaha ug katungod para mupili sa ilahang mga storya ug pag desisyon, ga tabang sa ilaha arun maka tuon ug mafeel proud sa ilahang gitrabaho. (IDI-01)

(I let students do a lot of the work themselves, but I am there to help if they need it. Giving them the freedom to choose their stories and make decisions helps them learn and feel proud of their work)

Sharp (pseudonym) also mentioned that empowering students with autonomy cultivates a sense of ownership and responsibility and nurtures leadership skills for future endeavors. He stated:

“I believe sa importansya sa paghatag ug katungod sa mga estudyante para mu-unlad ang ownership ug responsibility. Ang students kase kay gina encouraged na siya ang lead role sa tanan gikan sa pagpili ug storya hantod sa pag design sa layout”. (IDI-02).

(I believe in the importance of granting autonomy to students to foster ownership and responsibility. Students are encouraged to take lead roles in everything from story selection to layout design.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of advisers in managing school papers?

In the second question, participants were asked about their experiences as a school paper adviser. The following themes stated below

were thoroughly analyzed and were carefully reflected.

Recognizing and Motivating Students to Development

Actively identifying each student's strengths, interests, and areas for growth through regular feedback and assessments. Acknowledging their achievements and providing constructive criticism, the adviser encourages continuous improvement and professionalism in journalistic practices. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared that by acknowledging and celebrating their accomplishments—whether through publishing impactful articles, conducting insightful interviews, or receiving accolades—educators inspire students to strive for journalistic excellence continually. This positive reinforcement boosts their confidence and morale and validates their dedication and hard work. She said:

“Motivating and inspiring students to excel in their journalistic tasks involves recognizing their efforts and achievements while nurturing their passion. I celebrate their successes, whether it's publishing a compelling article, conducting a powerful interview, or receiving recognition for their work.” (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also revealed that mistakes and lapses are inevitable parts of the learning process, providing valuable opportunities for growth and refinement. Educators reinforce students' confidence and commitment to excellence by celebrating well-crafted articles and impactful contributions. He stated that:

“The kids strive harder when they are recognized, and although naa silay mga mistake and lapses but that's how they learn so kung naa silay mabuhat na artciles which is good, as much as possible we compliment it then provide a constructive criticism.” (IDI-02)

(The kids strive harder when they are recognized; although they make mistakes and have lapses, that is how they learn. So, if they create good articles, we try to compliment them as much as possible and then provide constructive criticism.)

Minimizing Adviser Influence on Student Work

It was revealed in the interview that by stepping back and encouraging students to lead the brainstorming, writing, editing, and design processes, the adviser helps build their confidence and problem-solving skills. Reducing the impact of advisors on student work is a calculated move that gives student journalists complete control over their magazines and encourages objectivity and honesty in their reporting.

Buttercup (pseudonym) shared with the researcher that she emphasizes the importance of critically evaluating information and seeking diverse perspectives; educators equip students with essential skills for distinguishing facts from opinions and ensuring balanced reporting. She said:

“I prioritize transparency, objectivity, and ethical journalism practices. I encourage students to evaluate information critically, seek diverse perspectives, and adhere to accuracy, fairness, and integrity principles in their reporting.” (IDI-01)

Additionally, Sharp (pseudonym) shared the same thoughts. He said that maintaining a hands-off approach while students write is essential to preserving their creative autonomy and fostering independent thinking in journalism. Refraining from undue influence, educators create a space where students feel empowered to explore diverse perspectives and develop their unique storytelling voices. He shared:

“To avoid influencing the student's output no, the coach should use a hands-off approach during or while ga write ang students.” (IDI-02)

(To avoid influencing the students' output, the coach should take a hands-off approach while the students are writing.)

Building a Strong Team

During the interviews, it was found that for a school paper adviser, building a good team is a key tactic necessary to develop a coherent and successful journalism program. The approach fosters critical thinking and self-motivation, enabling students to assume responsibility for their journalistic journey from ideation to dissemination. Buttercup (pseudonym) shares that she emphasizes the value of teamwork and respecting diverse perspectives, which cultivates a collaborative and inclusive atmosphere essential for compelling journalism. She said:

“I also emphasize the importance of teamwork and respect for diverse perspectives, fostering a positive and inclusive environment.” (IDI-01)

Finally, Sharp (pseudonym) supported Buttercup by adding that he reinforces the importance of teamwork as a mentor is crucial in fostering a collaborative and cohesive journalistic environment. Encouraging students to recognize and appreciate their roles and responsibilities cultivates a sense of accountability and mutual respect within the team. He stated:

“One more thing, as a mentor, I always remind my students about how teamwork makes the dream work. Each of them has an important role and responsibility to play.” (IDI-02)

Prioritizing Open Communication

Regular team meetings, open forums, and one-on-one check-ins allow continuous dialogue and ensure everyone is informed and engaged in the publication process. This open exchange of ideas helps identify and resolve issues quickly, promotes creative problem-solving, and ensures that all voices are heard and valued.

Buttercup (pseudonym) told the researcher that she said that building an environment of collaboration and efficiency with students in the school newspaper adviser role requires encouraging open communication and teamwork. By prioritizing open lines of communication, teachers empower students to express their opinions, worries, and suggestions openly. She revealed:

“As a school paper adviser, I prioritize open communication and collaboration with my students... We establish clear expectations and deadlines, ensuring that everyone knows their responsibilities”. (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) supported the previous statement that establishing clear and effective communication between mentors and students is crucial in maximizing the potential of each writer. He said:

“Importante jud na nay good communication si mentor and si student, so that aware si mentor about the capabilities of his writer, to know if the task is too difficult or not. We can achieve good outcome if we communicate.” (IDI-02)

(It is really important for the mentor and the student to have good communication so that the mentor is aware of the writer's capabilities and can determine if the task is too difficult or not. We can achieve good outcomes if we communicate.)

Encountering Challenges in Generating Interest and Recruiting Members

The interviews revealed that encountering challenges in forming a student-run paper is a common experience for a school paper adviser, requiring resilience, adaptability, and strategic problem-solving. Initial challenges often include recruiting a dedicated team, balancing varying skill levels, and managing time constraints amidst academic responsibilities.

Buttercup (pseudonym) articulated that overcoming the challenge of generating interest and recruiting dedicated students for the publication team requires strategic outreach and fostering a compelling vision. She said:

“One challenge is generating interest and recruiting students to join the publication team... It is also hard building a core team who were not only interested in journalism but also dependable and capable of handling responsibilities was crucial.” (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also mentioned that he manages deadlines and ensures regular contributions to the publication requires careful coordination and flexibility. Establishing a consistent workflow and fostering commitment among students balancing various academic and extracurricular activities can be a significant challenge for a school paper adviser. He stated:

“Isa sa challenges a school paper adviser may encounter is also establishing a consistent workflow and commitment among students who were balancing multiple academic and extracurricular commitments.” (IDI-02)

(One of the challenges a school paper adviser may encounter is establishing a consistent workflow and commitment among students who are balancing multiple academic and extracurricular commitments.)

Nurturing Growth and Purpose by Providing Constructive Feedback

Constructive feedback encourages a growth mindset, where students see challenges as opportunities to learn and develop. It also fosters a sense of purpose as students recognize the impact of their work and their role in informing and engaging their community.

Regular feedback sessions create an open dialogue between the adviser and the students, promoting trust and mutual respect. Buttercup (pseudonym) told the researcher that offering constructive feedback and encouragement is essential in guiding students toward improvement and resilience in their journalistic pursuits. She mentioned:

“Ga provide pud kog constructive feedback and encouragement, na makatabang sail aba to identify areas for growth and supporting them in overcoming challenges. Usa pa, I foster a sense of purpose by connecting journalism sa mga real world issues and empowering students to make difference through their reporting.” (IDI-01)

(I also provide constructive feedback and encouragement, helping students identify areas for growth and supporting them in overcoming challenges. Moreover, I foster a sense of purpose by connecting journalism to real-world issues and empowering students to make a difference through their reporting.)

It was reinforced by Sharp (pseudonym) that guiding students based on journalistic standards and best practices ensures integrity and professionalism in their work. Providing feedback rooted in these standards helps students understand the importance of adhering to professional norms rather than personal biases or preferences. He shared:

“Provide guidance and feedback based on journalistic standards and best practices, rather than personal preferences or biases.” (IDI-02)

Research Question No. 3: How do the adviser cope with the challenges they faced with regards to handling school paper organization

After conversing with the informants, the researcher established the following emerging themes: advisers' commitment to continuous professional growth for effective journalism advising, balancing workload, seeking administrative support, and practicing effective resource management.

Advisers' Commitment to Continuous Professional Growth for Effective Journalism Advising

According to them, advisers engage in continuous professional development through workshops, conferences, and networking with other journalism educators to cope with the evolving demands of student journalism. Staying current with the latest trends in media, technology, and educational strategies allows advisers to bring fresh perspectives and tools to their students. This was revealed by the participants when they were interviewed by the researcher. Buttercup (pseudonym) exposed that:

“Improving my own journalistic knowledge and skills is essential for effectively advising the school paper and staying current with the trends. I engage in continuous professional development through reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars.” (IDI-01)

Also, it was supported by Sharp (pseudonym), who said that ongoing learning allows them to bring current insights and techniques back to the classroom, enriching the educational experience for students. It demonstrates a commitment to lifelong learning and professional growth, inspiring students to adopt a similar mindset of curiosity and exploration in their journalistic pursuits. He said:

“Engage in continuous professional development through reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars.” (IDI-02)

Balancing Workload

Advisers often juggle teaching duties, administrative tasks, and overseeing the school paper's production, making it essential to prioritize and delegate tasks effectively. By finding a balance, advisers can maintain their well-being while providing consistent support and guidance to their students, ensuring the successful and timely production of the school paper. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared that advisers must allocate time effectively to fulfill both classroom duties and advisory roles, ensuring that each receives the attention necessary for student success. Balancing teaching responsibilities with advising the school paper demands adept time management, clear communication, and collaborative efforts. She articulated:

“Balancing teaching workloads and advising the school paper requires effective time management, communication, and collaboration”. (IDI-01)

Moreover, Sharp (pseudonym) supported Buttercup by adding that by carefully scheduling tasks, deadlines, and meetings, advisers can prioritize responsibilities and allocate sufficient time to each role. Effective time management enables mentors to provide timely feedback, support, and encouragement to students, fostering their growth and development as aspiring journalists. He stated:

“Organize a planner, being a mentor and a teacher can be both challenging so it is important to have good time management”. (IDI-02)

Seeking Administrative Support

Building strong relationships with school administrators and advisers can secure necessary resources, such as funding for equipment, software, and field trips, which are essential for a high-functioning journalism program. Advocating for the paper's role in the school community and its educational value helps gain administrative backing. Buttercup (pseudonym) believes that by cultivating strong relationships with colleagues and administrators, educators can leverage collective expertise and support to enhance student learning experiences and achieve shared objectives. She emphasizes:

“I maintain open lines of communication with colleagues and administrators to ensure mutual understanding and support for my dual roles.” (IDI-01)

Also, Sharp (pseudonym) supported Buttercup by adding that colleagues play a vital role in supporting advisers, providing invaluable advice and assistance during challenging times. Their expertise and perspectives can offer fresh insights and solutions to navigate various classroom and administrative issues effectively. He stated:

“Colleagues have an important role to us teachers, especially in times where we need additional support or advice on how to handle problems that are being encountered.” (IDI-02)

Practicing Effective Resource Management

Advisers must prioritize expenditures, focusing on essential items such as printing costs, software subscriptions, and necessary equipment while seeking cost-effective solutions where possible. Fundraising activities, sponsorships, and grants can supplement the budget, providing additional financial support. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared that by actively participating in general assemblies and special meetings, educators can highlight their programs' specific needs and priorities, including the school paper and other

extracurricular activities. This partnership allows educators to communicate the impact of these resources on student development and academic success, garnering support and investment from stakeholders. She stated:

"I work closely with school administrators and parent-teacher association to advocate for funding and resources, especially during general assembly and special meetings." (IDI-01)

Moreover, Sharp (pseudonym) also shared that securing financial and administrative support for the school paper requires educators to build strong relationships with key stakeholders, including administrators, faculty, parents, and local businesses. He revealed:

"School papers have a huge contribution to the school, and securing financial and administrative support for the school paper involves building relationships with key stakeholders and demonstrating the publication's value to the school community." (IDI-02)

Research Question No. 4: What insights can the advisers share that may be helpful to other school paper advisers and school administrators?

In the fourth question, participants were asked what are their insights they could share with other school paper advisers and school administrators. The following themes stated below were thoroughly analyzed and were carefully reflected.

Equipping Students for Online Journalism

Advisers must ensure students understand online platforms' unique challenges and opportunities, including ethical considerations, audience engagement strategies, and digital storytelling techniques. Advisers guide students on navigating digital tools and platforms effectively, emphasizing the importance of accuracy, credibility, and responsible use of social media. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared that preparing students for the realm of online journalism requires a comprehensive approach that integrates digital literacy, ethical guidelines, and awareness of media evolution. She said:

"Preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of online journalism involves equipping them with digital literacy skills, ethical guidelines, and an understanding of the evolving media landscape." (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also revealed that in today's digital age, it's necessary to equip young journalists with robust digital literacy skills. Mastering online tools and platforms empowers them to enhance their reporting and storytelling capabilities significantly. He stated:

"Oo syempre kay in today's digital age, equipping our young journalists with essential digital literacy skills is important. Dapat they know how to navigate and utilize various online tools and platforms not only to enhance their reporting and storytelling capabilities but also ensures they can effectively reach and engage with their audience." (IDI-02)

(Yes, of course, because in today's digital age, equipping our young journalists with essential digital literacy skills is important. They should know how to navigate and utilize various online tools and platforms not only to enhance their reporting and storytelling capabilities but also to ensure they can effectively reach and engage with their audience.)

Connecting to Broader Trends

It was revealed in the interview that advisers encourage students to explore and report on local manifestations of national or global trends, helping readers understand how broader issues affect their community. This approach not only enhances the paper's credibility but also educates students on the interconnectedness of local and global events. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared with the researcher that she encourages students to seek out compelling stories within the school community that go beyond mere reporting. She articulated:

"I encourage students to seek out interesting stories within the school community and explore the diverse interests and activities of their peers, highlighting the advocacy not just reporting an event." (IDI-01)

Additionally, Sharp (pseudonym) shared the same thoughts. He said that encouraging students to observe their surroundings, ask probing questions, and actively listen to the stories of their peers is foundational to cultivating their journalistic curiosity and skills. He mentioned:

"Encourage students to observe their surroundings, ask questions, and listen to the stories of their peers." (IDI-02)

Showcasing School Achievements

During the interviews, it was found that school paper advisers can effectively build school spirit, highlight student accomplishments, and cultivate a sense of pride among the student body by showcasing school victories. Advisors contribute to enhancing positive impressions of the institution by presenting these accomplishments through captivating narratives and eye-catching layouts. Buttercup (pseudonym) shares that highlighting the success stories and achievements of past and current student journalists serves as a powerful motivator and source of inspiration for aspiring reporters. She stated:

"Additionally, I highlight success stories and achievements of past and current student journalists, demonstrating the impact and recognition they have received within the school community and beyond." (IDI-01)

Moreover, Sharp (pseudonym) supported Buttercup by adding that journalism serves as a powerful tool to spotlight the achievements

and initiatives of various clubs, teams, and programs within a school community. He said:

“Journalism can be used to highlight the achievements and initiatives of different clubs, teams, and programs by showcasing their stories compellingly and engagingly.” (IDI-02)

Collaborative Brainstorming with the Colleague and School Administrator

It was revealed in the interview that by involving fellow educators and administrators in brainstorming sessions, advisers can gain diverse perspectives on potential story ideas, themes, and coverage angles that resonate with both students and the broader school community. Collaboration ensures that the school paper reflects the interests, achievements, and concerns that are relevant to all stakeholders. Buttercup (pseudonym) shared with the researcher that by organizing recruitment events, inviting guest speakers, and facilitating workshops, they showcase the transformative impact of journalism education. She said:

“As an adviser, I collaborate with school administrators and teachers to raise awareness about the school paper and its role in promoting student voice, critical thinking, and civic engagement. This may include organizing recruitment events, guest speaker presentations, or workshops to showcase the value of journalism education.” (IDI-01)

Finally, Sharp (pseudonym) shared the same thoughts. He said that establishing strong communication channels and building relationships with these stakeholders ensures that the achievements and contributions of various clubs, teams, and programs are effectively highlighted. He shared:

“I collaborate with club coordinators, coaches, and program coordinators to gather information and ensure accurate representation of their initiatives in the school paper.” (IDI-02)

Case 2 – Baltazar

This case is composed of two participants, with two females. All of them are school paper advisers and were selected as the research participants for the study.

Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School is located in Capungagan, Kapalong, Davao del Norte; like any other school, they have joined various competitions that include journalism, and they have their own school paper organization. The school has continually produced talented students who excelled in various fields.

These high school teachers are teachers who are school paper advisers. They understand that being a school paper adviser is a whirlwind of emotions. You are a coach guiding eager students, a mentor shaping young journalists, and sometimes even a therapist navigating creative clashes. It's stressful, balancing deadlines and resources, yet incredibly rewarding. The adviser serves as an educator who guides students through the process of journalistic writing, editing, and publication. They provide instruction on journalistic ethics, writing styles, and research techniques. This guidance helps students develop their skills in writing, critical thinking, and communication.

School Paper adviser revealed that being a school paper adviser the role of a school paper adviser is vital in fostering a dynamic and educational environment within a school's journalism or media program. Beyond academic guidance, advisers are crucial in supporting students personally and professionally. They act as mentors who encourage students to explore their interests, express their opinions, and develop confidence in their writing abilities. Upholding ethical standards in journalism is a critical responsibility of the adviser. They educate students on the importance of accuracy, fairness, and transparency in reporting.

Research Question No. 1: What unique strategies do successful school paper advisers employ to foster a thriving environment for journalism within their educational institutions?

Based on the first question, there are many themes that the researcher found. The following are the themes that have emerged which the researcher reflected and analyzed.

Fostering Students Interest

As a school paper adviser, you can encourage student interest in journalism by creating an atmosphere that highlights the fundamental benefits of journalism and its practical applications. Nurturing a culture that values critical thinking, research, and ethical standards in journalism helps students understand its importance in society. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that incorporating collaborative projects where students can work in teams to create their own news stories, fosters a sense of community and shared purpose. She said:

“To ignite interest sa journalism sa mga students, labi na kadtong mga dili interested, sugdan nako sa pagpakita sa lain-laing paagi sa storytelling, from traditional articles to multimedia presentations, Dayon, encourage them to explore various topics and issues they feel passionate about, reminding them sa role sa journalism in shedding light on important issues.” (IDI-03)

(To ignite interest in journalism among students, especially those who are not interested, I start by showcasing different ways of storytelling, from traditional articles to multimedia presentations. Then, I encourage them to explore various topics and issues they feel passionate about, reminding them of journalism's role in shedding light on important issues.)

Calm (pseudonym) also added that providing opportunities for hands-on experiences and practical learning, like field trips and guest speakers can help students develop their skills in gathering stories, protecting data, and critical thinking. She stated:

“Provide opportunities for hands-on experiences and practical learning, like field trips ug guest speakers. Through these activities, students develop their skills sa pagkuha og mga kwento, pagpanalipod sa mga data, ug critical thinking” (IDI-04)

(Provide opportunities for hands-on experiences and practical learning, like field trips and guest speakers. Through these activities, students develop their skills in gathering stories, protecting data, and critical thinking.)

Encouraging Student Independence

Encouraging student independence as a school paper adviser involves creating an environment where students are empowered to take initiative and make editorial decisions. Advisors help students develop a feeling of ownership and accountability by putting their trust in them to handle their tasks. This helps students get ready for careers in journalism or other areas that emphasize independence and leadership. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that by involving the students in discussions about media ethics and the impact of journalism on society, they develop a deeper understanding of the power and influence they hold as future journalists. He shared:

“It teaches them not just about the subject matter, but also about responsibility and accountability. Kini makahatag saila og sense sa empowerment nga mahimong motibasyon alang sa ilang pagtuon. students can explore ilang mga gipasaligan ug passions.” (IDI-03)

(It teaches them not just about the subject matter, but also about responsibility and accountability. This can give them a sense of empowerment that can motivate their studies. Students can explore their commitments and passions.)

Another point stated by Calm (pseudonym) is that by encouraging independence and critical thinking, students learn to navigate challenges and solve problems on their own. She said:

“Allow the students to be responsible of their own learning kay ang mentor is just a guide on the side lang man, sometimes they might make mistakes, but that's how they learn. Still, keep an eye on things to make sure the quality of our publication stays high.” (IDI-04)

(Allow the students to be responsible for their own learning because the mentor is just a guide on the side, and sometimes they might make mistakes, but that is how they learn. Still, keep an eye on things to make sure the quality of our publication stays high.)

Storytelling through Multimedia Integration

During the interviews, it was revealed that by integrating multimedia, students can produce more dynamic and impactful stories that appeal to a broader audience and reflect the multifaceted nature of contemporary journalism. Advisers teach students how to use multimedia tools and platforms effectively, emphasizing the importance of visual and auditory elements in capturing audience attention and conveying complex information. Brainy (pseudonym) articulated that by incorporating digital tools such as video editing software, social media analytics, and content management systems, advisers ensure that the students are well-versed in the latest industry practices. She confirmed:

“We also guide them sa paggamit sa mga teknolohiya ug tools for journalism, helping them adapt sa mga bag-ong platform ug trends. Through experiential learning experiences ug practical projects, we prepare students sa mga aktuwal nga short ug long-form journalism assignments.” (IDI-03)

(We also guide them in using technologies and tools for journalism, helping them adapt to new platforms and trends. Through experiential learning experiences and practical projects, we prepare students for actual short and long-form journalism assignments.)

Calm (pseudonym) supported the previous statement that they are in the 21st century, so the students should also have exposure to modern technology used in journalism. This hands-on experience with modern tools ensures they can create compelling, multimedia-rich content that meets contemporary audience expectations. She said:

“Integrating modern technologies and tools into our journalism curriculum is essential in equipping students with the skills necessary to thrive in a constantly evolving media landscape. We are in a 21st century naman, so dapat naa sad silay exposure sa modern technology na ginagamit sa journalism.” (IDI-04)

(Integrating modern technologies and tools into our journalism curriculum is essential in equipping students with the skills necessary to thrive in a constantly evolving media landscape. We are in the 21st century, so they should also have exposure to modern technology used in journalism.)

Building a Foundation for Student Journalism

Advisers provide comprehensive training in essential journalistic techniques like research, interviewing, writing, and editing. They also emphasize the importance of understanding and respecting different perspectives, fostering critical thinking and analytical skills. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that providing workshops and training sessions to hone the student's abilities in writing and gathering information. She stated:

“To ready students for the demands of school journalism, we equip them with practical skills like news writing, interviewing, and research. Kami usahay maghatag og workshops ug training sessions to hone ilang mga abilidad sa pagsulat ug pagkuha og impormasyon. We also teach them about journalistic ethics ug responsibility.” (IDI-03)

(You can ask our co-mathematics teachers about their strategies. This way, we can gather different strategies from them and apply them ourselves.)

Moreover, Calm (pseudonym) also shared that workshops cover various aspects of journalism, from understanding news values and structuring articles to conducting effective interviews and fact-checking. She said:

“The students have the potential man to write and create, we just have to train. To do that, implement ang mga school paper adviser ug training workshops and activities, give the students a strong foundation on how to do good writing and become a good journalist.” (IDI-04)

(The students have the potential to write and create, we just have to train them. To do that, school paper advisers implement training workshops and activities, giving the students a strong foundation on how to write well and become good journalists.)

Finding Relevance of the Story to the Community

Focusing on stories that reflect the community's real-life challenges, achievements, and aspirations, students learn to create content that is meaningful and impactful. Students must actively participate in their community, listen to its members, and determine the topics that are most important to them in order to apply this strategy. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that by encouraging students to discern newsworthy stories through a multifaceted lens, the adviser aims to cultivate a critical understanding of how impactful journalism intersects with audience engagement and societal relevance. She confirmed:

“In guiding my students toward discerning newsworthy stories, I instill a multifaceted approach, emphasizing the exploration of topics that not only captivate their audience but also possess intrinsic value by addressing pressing issues.” (IDI-03)

Calm (pseudonym) supported the previous statement that impactful journalism requires students to choose important subjects that connect with their audience and add to the public conversation. She stated:

“Imohang i-encourage students to choose meaningful topics that connect with their audience and add value to public conversations, like if the news is relevant ba or not.” (IDI-04)

(You should encourage students to choose meaningful topics that connect with their audience and add value to public conversations, like determining if the news is relevant or not.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of advisers in managing school papers?

In the second question, many themes were discovered, and the following are the themes that emerged: Prioritize Open Communication, Implementing Practices in School Journalism, Recognizing and Motivating Students Development, and Encountering Challenges in Forming a Student-Run Paper.

Prioritize Open Communication

In the interviews, it was revealed that prioritizing open communication cultivates a supportive atmosphere that enhances both the quality of the school paper and the growth and development of its student journalists. emphasizing clarity and openness, advisers help students develop strong interpersonal skills and a sense of mutual respect. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that by working together closely, both parties can ensure that they share a common understanding and goal, facilitating constructive feedback and suggestions for enhancing the quality of writing. She shared:

“Work together aron pagtambag og balansehan ang mga ideya ug responsibilidad. There should be an open communication between the adviser and the journalist to ensure na same phase, na even if they have their own idea the teacher can still comment or suggest to make the writing better.” (IDI-03)

(Work together to advise and balance ideas and responsibilities. There should be open communication between the adviser and the journalist to ensure they are on the same page, so even if they have their own ideas, the teacher can still comment or suggest improvements to make the writing better.)

Calm (pseudonym) also added that when there is open and clear communication between team members, ideas flow more freely, misunderstandings are minimized, and collaboration becomes more cohesive. She stated:

“We should also have good communication, kay when both of us are communicating mas effective and teamwork that could have a positive impact in making a good output.” (IDI-04)

(We should also have good communication, because when both of us are communicating, it is more effective and teamwork that could have a positive impact in producing a good output.)

Implementing Practices in School Journalism

By incorporating editorial calendars, regular staff meetings, and deadline management, advisers help students understand the importance of organization and time management. Encouraging peer reviews and collaborative editing processes fosters a culture of constructive feedback and continuous improvement. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that flexibility allows for student input and leadership, fostering creativity and ownership in their journalistic endeavors. By maintaining a structured editorial process, such as through regular meetings and workshops on journalistic ethics and techniques, students benefit from a framework that guides their work while ensuring they understand professional standards. She emphasized:

“One of my key best practices is maintaining a structured yet flexible editorial process that allows for student input and leadership. This includes regular editorial meetings, workshops on journalistic ethics and techniques, and peer review sessions.” (IDI-03)

Another point stated by Calm (pseudonym) is that by focusing on journalistic skills and rigorous fact-checking practices, the advisers ensure that accuracy remains paramount in reporting. She mentioned:

“Naay regular training workshops to enhance journalistic skills, promote rigorous fact-checking to ensure accuracy, and encourage interdisciplinary projects that integrate various academic perspectives into our reporting to enrich content and engage a broader audience.” (IDI-04)

(There are regular training workshops to enhance journalistic skills, promote rigorous fact-checking to ensure accuracy, and encourage interdisciplinary projects that integrate various academic perspectives into our reporting to enrich content and engage a broader audience.)

Recognizing and Motivating Students' Development

During the interviews, it was revealed that advisers can motivate students by setting challenging yet attainable goals, offering leadership roles, and encouraging participation in journalism workshops or competitions. Providing constructive feedback and highlighting each student's unique contributions, advisers help build confidence and a sense of accomplishment. Brainy (pseudonym) articulated the adviser's supportive role in student journalism by actively involving students in the publication process and recognizing their contributions. Asking students if they want to see their work in articles, the adviser not only encourages a sense of ownership and motivation but also ignites their passion for journalistic excellence. She stated:

“I always asked og gusto ba nila makita ilang work sa mga articles? So that we can Ignite as an adviser the flame inside saila, I used that para mamotivate ang student. As much as possible I acknowledge their work and recognize the improvement in their paper.” (IDI-03)

(I always ask if they want to see their work in the articles. As an adviser, I use that to ignite the flame inside them and motivate the students. As much as possible, I acknowledge their work and recognize the improvement in their paper.)

Calm (pseudonym) supported the previous statement by stating that recognition not only validates the hard work put into their journalistic endeavors but also encourages a sense of pride and achievement among students. She said:

“As a coach, I know unsa ka challenging ug lisod magbuhat ug articles or even sa mga editorial cartooning it is very challenging so I try to recognize the work of students, whether through awards, publication acknowledgments, or class showcases to help them build confidence and motivation na mas maganahan pa sila mu do sailing work.” (IDI-04)

(As a coach, I know how challenging and difficult it is to create articles or even editorial cartoons, so I try to recognize the work of students, whether through awards, publication acknowledgments, or class showcases, to help them build confidence and motivation so they become even more eager to do their work.)

Encountering Challenges in Generating Interest and Recruiting Member

The interviews revealed that one primary challenge is securing consistent student participation and commitment, as students often juggle multiple responsibilities. Ensuring a steady flow of high-quality content can be difficult, especially as students may lack experience in journalism. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that common challenge in initiating a student-run school paper: garnering sufficient interest and participation from students. This challenge often arises due to varying levels of enthusiasm, competing priorities, or initial skepticism about the feasibility and benefits of such a venture. She revealed:

“During the initial stages sa pag-buo ug pag-organize sa school-run school paper, isa ka specific challenge na akong gi atubang kay ang pag himok mismo sa interest ug participation sa students.” (IDI-03)

(During the initial stages of forming and organizing a student-run school paper, one specific challenge I faced was rallying enough interest and participation from students.)

Calm (pseudonym) also added that the additional challenge in recruiting new members for school journalism is overcoming the misconception that it is an exclusive domain reserved only for the brightest students. This perception can deter many potential participants who may feel they lack the necessary skills or intellectual prowess to contribute effectively. She emphasized:

“Students think that joining journalism is hard, kay para rana sya sa mga bright bright, and that is one of the challenges gyod ang pag recruit ug new members and honing their abilities, kay every year mag train naman sad kag mga studyane na mupuli sa mga nang graduate.” (IDI-04)

(Students think that joining journalism is hard because it is just for those who are very bright, and that is one of the real challenges in recruiting new members and honing their abilities because every year you end up training students who will replace those who have graduated.)

Research Question No. 3: How do the advisers cope with the challenges they face with regard to handling school paper organization?

At this point, participants were asked about how they cope with the challenges they have experienced. The following themes stated below were thoroughly analyzed and were carefully reflected.

Practicing Effective Resource Management

Advisers often exemplify resource management principles by efficiently allocating time, materials, and human resources. They implement strategies such as digital documentation systems to minimize paper waste and streamline access to information. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that articulating clear objectives and strategies for resource allocation, such as improving equipment, expanding distribution channels, or funding training workshops, the presentation demonstrates accountability and foresight. She stated:

“Kinahanglan nako nga magpakita og klaro ug maayong plano sa paggamit sa pondo ug mga resources. I also highlight the benefits and value that the school paper brings to the institution, emphasizing its role in student development and community engagement.” (IDI-03)

(I must present a clear and reasonable plan for using funds and resources. I also highlight the benefits and value that the school paper brings to the institution, emphasizing its role in student development and community engagement.)

Calm (pseudonym) supported the previous statement by stating the pivotal role of school stakeholders, notably the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA), in securing financial support for the school paper. The school paper can access necessary funds for operational expenses, equipment upgrades, and educational resources by cultivating strong relationships and garnering backing from these critical stakeholders through fundraising initiatives, sponsorship opportunities, or direct contributions. She revealed:

“Sa suporta sa school’s stakeholders sama sa PTA, among ma secure ang funds para sa school paper” (IDI-04)

(Through the support of the school’s stakeholders, like ang PTA. We can secure funds for the school paper.)

Fostering Students' Development in Journalism

By providing guidance on research techniques, writing styles, and journalistic ethics, advisers empower students to produce high-quality content that informs and engages their peers and the broader school community. Advisers foster an environment where aspiring journalists can develop critical thinking, ethical reporting, and practical communication skills. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that by focusing on news writing, interviewing techniques, and research methods, the educator facilitates immersive learning opportunities that prepare students for real-world journalism. This equips students with essential technical skills but also fosters critical thinking, communication abilities, and ethical awareness necessary for compelling journalism. She said:

"I can help students improve their journalistic skills and knowledge by providing hands-on training and practical experiences in news writing, interviewing techniques, and research methods." (IDI-03)

Calm (pseudonym) expressed that a comprehensive approach nurtures students' journalistic skills and knowledge by combining practical experience with mentorship and structured learning. She stated:

"Helping students improve their journalistic skills and knowledge involves a combination of hands-on experience, mentorship, and structured learning opportunities. I provide ongoing feedback and guidance on their writing, reporting, and storytelling techniques, emphasizing the importance of accuracy, fairness, and ethical conduct." (IDI-04)

Balancing Workload

Aside from supervising editorial content and scheduling, advisers also have to mentor student reporters and ensure publication deadlines are fulfilled. Keeping everyone on track necessitates having the acute ability to assign duties when it makes sense, prioritize tasks, and keep lines of communication open. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that by allocating specific blocks of time for each duty, the educator ensures that both teaching and advising roles receive the necessary attention and dedication. She stated:

"I allocate specific blocks of time for both teaching and advising duties, ensuring that each aspect receives adequate attention." (IDI-03)

Calm (pseudonym) supported Brainy by emphasizing the importance of maintaining a balanced approach and effective time

management. As an adviser, one is tasked with guiding students through journalistic processes, offering feedback, and ensuring the quality of publications. She shared:

“Balance your responsibility kay dili man ka adviser lang sa school paper, you are also a teacher. Dapat nakay time management.” (IDI-04)

(Balance your responsibility because you are not just an adviser to the school paper but also a teacher. You should have good time management.)

Adviser's Commitment to Continuous Professional Growth for Effective Journalism Advising

Advisers often need continuous professional growth, which involves staying updated on evolving media trends, journalistic standards, and educational methodologies. They benefit from mentorship opportunities, professional networks, and access to resources that enhance their editorial and managerial skills. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that she continually expands their knowledge base and refines their skills through these educational opportunities; the adviser ensures they are well-prepared to support and mentor students effectively in their journalistic endeavors. She stated:

"I strive to expand my knowledge base and refine my craft as an adviser; I attend workshops, conferences, and seminars related to journalism. Through these efforts, I ensure that I am well-equipped to support and mentor students effectively in their journalistic pursuits." (IDI-03)

Furthermore, Calm (pseudonym) added that through regular participation in workshop training and continuous pursuit of learning opportunities. By actively engaging in these activities, the educator aims to enhance their ability to effectively support and inspire student journalists. She shared:

"Regularly participate in workshop training to improve and actively seek opportunities for learning and growth. With this, I can enhance my ability to support and inspire student journalists." (IDI-04)

Research Question No. 3: What insights can the advisers share that may be helpful to other school paper advisers and school administrators?

Insights are so powerful that it takes just a piece of advice to help someone. In the fourth main question, the researcher established the following emerging themes:

Encouraging Student Participation in Campus Journalism, Showcasing School Achievements, Connecting to Broader Trends, and Empowering Students Through Digital Literacy in Journalism.

Encouraging Student Participation in Campus Journalism

Advisers understand the importance of creating a supportive environment where students feel empowered to voice their perspectives and investigate issues relevant to their school community. They recognize that nurturing student participation enriches the school paper's content and prepares students for future academic and professional pursuits, equipping them with valuable skills in research, storytelling, and ethical reporting. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that educators can effectively engage and motivate students by highlighting advantages such as the opportunity to develop writing skills, gain practical journalistic experience, and make meaningful contributions to the school community. She said:

"To encourage students to join the campus paper, it is vital to highlight the benefits of participation, such as honing writing skills, gaining journalistic experience, and contributing to the school community. Hosting workshops and seminars on journalism basics can pique interest and guide aspiring writers." (IDI-03)

Furthermore, Calm (pseudonym) added that encouraging student participation in the campus paper involves actively promoting the benefits and opportunities of engaging in student journalism. She revealed:

"Helping the school to encourage students to join the campus paper involves promoting the benefits and opportunities of participating in student journalism." (IDI-04)

Showcasing School Achievements

Advisers understand that celebrating extracurricular, academic, or community-focused successes builds student pride, school spirit, and community relationships. They take a calculated approach to sharing accomplishments, hoping to uplift and encourage kids while showcasing their many gifts and contributions. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that journalists play a crucial role in crafting narratives that document and celebrate the passion and commitment of individuals involved in these endeavors. By spotlighting these accomplishments through compelling storytelling, journalists can effectively communicate the significance and impact of each initiative to a broader audience. She shared:

"Journalism is a powerful tool in spotlighting the accomplishments and endeavors of various clubs, teams, and programs within a school community. By weaving narratives that capture the essence of their efforts, journalists can effectively convey the passion and

dedication behind each endeavor." (IDI-03)

Furthermore, Calm (pseudonym) added that by documenting these occurrences through articles, photographs, and features, the school paper not only preserves the memories of important events but also serves as a historical record of the school community's activities and achievements. She emphasized:

"Dako bya ug contribution ang school paper in telling the stories, especially pag nay mga events they capture moments." (IDI-04)

(The school paper contributes significantly to telling stories, especially when there are events, as they capture moments.)

Catered Varied Learning Needs of Students

Teachers foster student engagement, motivation, and success by recognizing and accommodating diverse learning needs. Catering to students' varied learning needs is essential for creating an inclusive, engaging, and equitable learning environment. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that students have different ways of understanding and processing information. By catering to varied learning needs, teachers provide multiple pathways to understanding and allow students to approach concepts from different angles. He confirmed:

"There is no single strategy that will fit all of your students. There is no single strategy that is effective for all of them. Some pedagogies are effective to many but not to all; some are effective to some and not to many." (IDI-03)

(There is no single strategy that will fit all of your students. There is no single strategy that is effective for all of them. Some pedagogies are compelling to many but not to all, and some pedagogies are effective to some and not to many)

Thin (pseudonym) expressed her feelings that students are more likely to be actively involved in the learning process when the instruction resonates with their learning styles, interests, and abilities. She said:

"Ang pedagogy sa teaching man gud, some of it in reality sa teaching some of it are effective sa bata, pero some are not ga depende jud sa bata like for example this strategy us effective sa kani na set of students or class but dili siya effective sa kani na class. That is why diba as a teacher we need many strategies because some strategies will not work sa tanan ga set of students." (IDI-04)

(The pedagogy of teaching, you see, in reality, some strategies are effective for children, while others are not. It depends on the child. For example, a particular strategy may be effective for one set of students or class but not for another. That is why, as teachers, we need multiple strategies; not all strategies will work for every set of students.)

Connecting to Broader Trends

Advisers understand that contextualizing local events within regional, national, or global frameworks gives students a broader perspective on their roles as informed citizens. They encourage student journalists to explore how school initiatives, policies, and events intersect with more prominent societal themes such as education reform, environmental sustainability, or social justice. Brainy (pseudonym) shared that by fostering curiosity and empathy, students are motivated to explore and understand the experiences and challenges of their peers, thereby uncovering compelling story ideas that resonate with their audience. She stated:

"I empower student journalists by encouraging them to immerse themselves in their communities, listening attentively to the narratives unfolding around them. By fostering curiosity and empathy, students can uncover compelling story ideas rooted in the experiences and challenges of their peers." (IDI-03)

Calm (pseudonym) supported Brainy by adding that by exploring various storytelling techniques, students can discover the most engaging and impactful ways to communicate their stories to readers. Whether through compelling storytelling or vivid imagery, these different formats allow students to bring achievements and events within their school community to life, capturing the attention and resonating with the interests of their audience. She shared:

"Encourage students to explore different storytelling formats and approaches, such as human-interest features, investigative reports, or opinion pieces, to find the most engaging and impactful way to tell their stories. ... through compelling storytelling and vivid imagery, these achievements can be brought to life, resonating with readers." (IDI-04)

Empowering Students Through Digital Literacy in Journalism

Empowering students through digital literacy in journalism, reflecting a recognition of the transformative impact of digital platforms on media consumption and production. Advisers prioritize equipping students with the skills to navigate and utilize digital tools effectively, from multimedia storytelling and social media engagement to data analysis and online publishing. Brainy (pseudonym) told the researcher that by equipping students with skills in digital news gathering and publication, the educator ensures they are adept at navigating the complexities of online media. It prepares them to engage with audiences across various online platforms while maintaining journalistic integrity and ethical standards. She stated:

"To prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of online journalism, I provide training on using digital tools and platforms for news gathering and publication." (IDI-03)

Lastly, Calm (pseudonym) added that by providing thorough instructions, students gain practical skills in navigating digital resources, conducting research, and organizing information efficiently. She emphasized:

“Para ma prepare sila, we provide thorough instructions on how to use digital tools and platforms for efficient news gathering and distribution.” (IDI-04)

(To prepare them, we provide thorough instructions on using digital tools and platforms for efficient news gathering and distribution.)

Case 3 – Kapalong

This case is composed of two participants, with two females. They were all school paper advisers and were selected as the research participants for this study.

Kapalong National High School is a school located in Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The school joined various competitions, such as journalism, and continues to have multiple awards. It has also sent students to a higher level of competition related to journalism.

School paper advisers who participate in journalism competitions improve their skills and become inspiring role models for their students. Joining these contests, they learn new techniques and ideas to share with their school papers. Their hard work often pays off, leading to many awards for the advisers and their student teams. These achievements celebrate the dedication of the advisers and showcase the talents they have nurtured in their students. This success creates a positive atmosphere in the school, emphasizing the value of good journalism and encouraging students to pursue their passion for storytelling confidently. Ultimately, these accomplishments highlight how strong leadership in school journalism can inspire a new generation of thoughtful and skilled journalists.

The High School paper advisers revealed that they play a crucial role in shaping the next generation of journalists by providing guidance, mentorship, and hands-on experience. Through their support, students develop critical research, writing, and ethical reporting skills, empowering them to become informed, responsible, and confident storytellers in their communities.

Research Question No. 1: What unique strategies do successful school paper advisers employ to foster a thriving environment for journalism within their educational institutions?

The researcher discovered several themes based on the first question. The following are the themes on which the researcher reflected and analyzed.

Encouraging Student Independence

The participants revealed during the interviews that successful school paper advisers often employ unique strategies to foster student independence. They cultivate an environment where students are encouraged to take ownership of their ideas and projects, guiding them to make autonomous decisions while providing support and constructive feedback. Bubbly (pseudonym) stated that while students have the freedom to tell their own stories, they must also bear the responsibility for the impact of their words. He said:

“Your story, your responsibility. That is how I guide my student writers. It always has to be in the light of freedom. Your freedom ends when the freedom of others begins.” (IDI-05)

Another point stated by Happy (pseudonym) is that granting autonomy to students fosters a transformative educational environment where they transition from passive learners to active creators of knowledge. He stated:

“ang paghatag og autonomy sa mga estudyante can lead empowers them to become not just learners, but creators of knowledge, nga may kakayahan sa paghimo og positibong kahimtang sa ilang kaugalingon.” (IDI-06)

(Giving autonomy to students can lead to empowering them to become not just learners, but creators of knowledge, capable of creating positive conditions for themselves.)

Finding Relevance of the Story to the Community

When advisers encourage students to explore topics that resonate with the school's local environment, addressing issues that impact their peers, teachers, and families, advisers facilitate discussions on the importance of community engagement and journalistic responsibility, guiding students to seek out stories that inform, inspire, or provoke thought within their immediate surroundings. Bubbly (pseudonym) shared that by prompting the students to observe their surroundings and current events actively, advisers stimulate curiosity and awareness of societal dynamics. He emphasizes:

“Let them observe, and I ask them to answer the following questions: What is new? What excites people now? What is the issue? What makes the conversation? How relevant is it to their audience?” (IDI-05)

Additionally, Happy (pseudonym) shared the same thoughts. He emphasizes the importance of capturing ideas or events clearly and comprehensively, particularly in cartooning. He confirmed:

“On knowledge, it would be how to capture an idea or an event clearly and comprehensively, most especially in cartooning. Relevant, current, interesting stories are all around, all the students need to do is capture it and make sure this capturing is holistic.” (IDI-06)

Practicing makes Writing Developed

The participants revealed during the interviews that advisers understand that consistent practice is essential for refining journalistic techniques, improving clarity, and honing storytelling abilities. By providing constructive feedback and encouraging revisions, they instill a culture of continuous improvement and resilience in their writers. Bubbly (pseudonym) stated that stresses the necessity of being open to new ideas, perspectives, and feedback. By continuously practicing and learning from both successes and failures, writers can refine their abilities and evolve creatively. He emphasized:

“I asked my writer to listen, read, investigate, write, critique and be open. Activities to hone their skills need to be all of the ones I mentioned. They need to practice, and practice and practice. Learn from others, from their mistakes. They will not be able to do that unless they are open.” (IDI-05)

Another point stated by Happy (pseudonym) is acknowledging that becoming an expert takes time and requires continuous honing of skills through practice and structured training workshops. He shared:

“Openness in learning is key, dili man dayon ma hawd ang mga bata, especially those students na bag o palang, so we have to hone their skills and abilities by practice and training workshop.” (IDI-06)

(Openness in learning is key. The students will not become experts right away, especially new ones, so we have to hone their skills and abilities through practice and training workshops.)

Cultivating Discipline and Open-Mindedness in Journalism Education

Establishing clear expectations and deadlines, teaching students the importance of meeting journalistic standards and deadlines while fostering a disciplined work ethic. Advisers encourage open-mindedness by exposing students to diverse perspectives, challenging them to explore topics from multiple angles, and considering viewpoints that may differ from their own. Bubbly (pseudonym) shared that by embracing openness, journalists can adapt to challenges, refine their skills, and deliver more impactful and insightful stories to their audience. He articulated:

“The skill of journalism is tough. Be disciplined, and come to interviews and events prepared, early, and with vigor. Being open-minded allows my students to be more creative and not sulk if their submissions are for revisions or scrap at all.” (IDI-05)

Moreover, Happy (pseudonym) also shared that without foundational skills, students cannot effectively progress in their learning and professional growth. Discipline ensures consistency in work habits, from research and fact-checking to writing and reporting, which are essential in producing accurate and compelling journalism. He stated:

“Instilling discipline and preparation in journalism is very important, kay di man mag grow ang student if di sya kabalo mudisiplina saiyang self” (IDI-06)

(Instilling discipline and preparation in journalism is very important, because a student will not grow if they do not know how to discipline themselves.)

Assisting Students in Idea Generation

During the interview, it was revealed that the school paper adviser encourages brainstorming sessions that are inclusive and non-judgmental, where every idea is considered valuable. These advisers also leverage their experience to suggest diverse approaches and perspectives, challenging students to explore unconventional angles. Bubbly (pseudonym) shared that the coach fosters a deeper understanding of compelling storytelling and engagement within journalism by showcasing successful examples and discussing their reception. He said:

“Therefore, it is important as a coach to show them a sample of works published already and how they were appreciated or have caused conversations. I want to have a discussion and collaboration where I can hear their ideas, and we can collaborate so that they can also learn from my perspective. I always believe in the inner drive, that gut feeling, which will help students find love in journalism.” (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) expressed her feelings by sharing that by working together, writers can benefit from diverse perspectives and insights that contribute to richer, more nuanced ideas. Collaborative efforts encourage brainstorming, constructive feedback, and the exchange of techniques and approaches, all of which can elevate writing projects' clarity, depth, and creativity. He stated:

“When you collaborate with your peers, you get ideas which will help you make good writing.” (IDI-06)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of advisers in managing school papers?

Many themes were discovered based on the second question, and the following themes emerged.

Defining Clearly the Roles and Responsibilities

In the interviews, it was revealed that by aligning assignments with students' interests and skill sets, advisors create a collaborative environment in which each student sees their strengths and opportunities for progress. Influential school paper advisers build a motivated and cohesive editorial team that regularly produces high-quality content by encouraging accountability and a sense of ownership among team members. Bubbly (pseudonym) shared that by adhering to deadlines and commitments, educators instill a sense of responsibility and accountability in their students. He revealed:

"If you say the deadline is this, ask them of the output. If you say I have my comments on this day, make sure that you will be able to do so. Students are motivated by your example." (IDI-05)

(If you say the deadline is a specific day, ask them for the output. If you say you have comments on this day, make sure you can provide them. Students are motivated by your example.)

Happy (pseudonym) added that by establishing clear parameters such as deadlines, topics, and expected outcomes, mentors provide students with a structured framework to work and achieve their objectives. This clarity minimizes ambiguity, aligns expectations, and empowers students to focus their efforts effectively. He said:

"Because it will help them both to set what needs to be set such as the deadlines, the topic, and gina expect ni mentor na outcomes sa gibuhat ni students." (IDI-06)

(Because it will help both to set what needs to be set, such as the deadlines, the topic, and the outcomes the mentor expects from the student's work.)

Recognizing and Motivating Students' Development

Influential advisors for school papers are adept at identifying and fostering students' growth through individualized guidance and support. By learning about each student's areas of strength, interest, and growth, they can customize feedback and advice. Bubbly (pseudonym) told the researcher that by valuing each student's contributions and ideas, educators foster a sense of belonging and appreciation, which motivates students to participate and excel actively. Celebrating small achievements acknowledges progress and reinforces positive behavior, boosting confidence and morale. He stated:

"To motivate and inspire students, I focus on creating an environment that values each student's contributions and ideas. Celebrating small wins and providing constructive feedback." (IDI-05)

Another point stated by Happy (pseudonym) is that recognizing that mistakes are integral to the learning process and providing constructive criticism helps students understand areas for improvement without discouraging them. He said:

"Students are motivated to do their work when their work and efforts are recognized. Though they make mistakes, that is how they learn, so you provide constructive criticism or feedback na di maka discourage sa ila. Moreover, by the way, food is a good motivation." (IDI-06)

(Students are motivated to do their work when their work and efforts are recognized. Though they make mistakes, that is how they learn, so you provide constructive criticism or feedback that does not discourage them. Moreover, by the way, food is a good motivator.)

Prioritize Open Communication

During the interviews, it was revealed that drawing from their own experiences and interactions with students, advisers emphasize creating a supportive environment where students feel comfortable expressing their ideas, concerns, and aspirations. They actively listen to students' perspectives, fostering mutual respect and trust through transparent dialogue. Bubbly (pseudonym) articulated that by engaging in dialogue with students, educators gain valuable insights into their circumstances, learning styles, and potential barriers. He confirmed:

"Also, talk to students. You must get to see the context of why the student struggles to write or has difficulty accomplishing a task." (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) supported the previous statement that communication enhances understanding and promotes creativity and critical thinking among students. By encouraging a flow of ideas and perspectives, educators create opportunities for collective learning and improvement in the quality of content produced. He said:

"Open communication creates a more inclusive and collaborative environment. When we communicate with them, we can flow ideas, feedback, and discussions to enhance the quality of the content produced." (IDI-06)

Minimizing Adviser Influence on Student Work

Advisers navigate the delicate balance between offering expertise and allowing students the autonomy to explore and develop their journalistic voice. Instead, they focus on mentorship that empowers students to make informed editorial decisions, offering constructive

feedback that encourages growth without overshadowing individual perspectives. Bubbly (pseudonym) shared that educators foster creativity and self-expression by allowing writers the space to explore and develop their unique style. Acknowledging that each writer possesses individual strengths and preferences should be nurtured rather than constrained. He articulated:

"As I mentioned, give my writers freedom and guide them in exercising their freedom. Let them explore their style. Every writer has one. We guide them but let them do what they feel like doing." (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) supported the previous statement that allowing students to work autonomously encourages them to take ownership of their work and develop problem-solving skills. By guiding from the sidelines, educators support students in navigating challenges and exploring their ideas while maintaining a sense of responsibility for their output. He mentioned:

"Allow them to work on their own, guide on the side lang bya si teacher. While we share our ideas, it is also important that they are responsible for the output that they are writing." (IDI-06)

(Allow them to work independently, with the teacher just guiding from the side. While we share our ideas, they must also be responsible for the output they are writing.)

Research Question No. 3: How do the advisers cope with the challenges they face with regard to handling school paper organization?

The participants were asked how they coped with the challenges they faced in the third main question of the research. The following themes were thoroughly examined and carefully considered.

Fostering Students' Development in Journalism

During the interview, it was revealed that advisers facilitate workshops, provide resources, and offer constructive feedback to enhance students' writing, editing, and investigative skills. They also encourage collaborative projects and peer mentoring to cultivate teamwork and journalistic integrity. Bubbly (pseudonym) told the researcher that participating in competitions provides valuable hands-on experience in real-world scenarios, where students can apply their knowledge and refine their journalistic techniques under pressure. He emphasizes:

"Also encourage students to pursue and attend journalism conferences, and participate in competitions like press conferences to develop their skills further and expand their networks." (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) also stated that exposure showcases effective storytelling techniques and journalistic standards and encourages students to aspire to achieve similar levels of excellence in their work. Attending seminars in journalism further enhances their understanding by offering insights from industry experts and discussing emerging trends and practices. He shared:

"Expose the students to winning papers, international papers, video tutorials, and attend seminars in journalism." (IDI-06)

Maintaining Journalistic Integrity

Thorough fact-checking, unbiased reporting, and adherence to established journalistic principles despite potential pressures or limitations. Advisers foster critical thinking among students, encouraging them to scrutinize sources, verify information rigorously, and uphold transparency in their writing. Bubbly (pseudonym) told the researcher that while content oversight is typically necessary to maintain journalistic integrity and educational standards, censorship to suppress factual information undermines transparency and ethical reporting. He confirmed:

"It is always normal for school papers to be censored on content to make sure that the truth comes out. However, it is a different issue when censorship happens to hide the truth. The latter happens. Discussing the issue with the person who sensors the material is essential." (IDI-05)

It was also supported by Happy (pseudonym), who stated that by emphasizing these principles, educators empower students to uphold journalistic integrity and resist external interference that may compromise the integrity of their work. He said:

"In cases where external parties attempt to interfere with the publication's content, I emphasize the importance of editorial independence and the role of the school paper as a platform for student expression." (IDI-06)

Balancing Workload

During the interview, it was revealed that advisers establish realistic timelines and checkpoints to monitor progress, offering support and guidance as needed to keep tasks on track. They also encourage students to take initiative and collaborate, fostering a sense of shared ownership and responsibility. By maintaining open lines of communication and leveraging teamwork, successful advisers navigate workload challenges while empowering students to develop valuable skills in time management and collaboration essential for their journalistic endeavors. Bubbly (pseudonym) said that by prioritizing teaching duties while allocating dedicated time for advising the school paper, educators ensure they fulfill both roles effectively. He said:

"It is all about time management. I make sure that I do first my job as a teacher and then devote time for my school paper adviser work." (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) also emphasizes the importance of maintaining a balanced approach to fulfilling responsibilities as a teacher while managing additional tasks, such as advising or coordinating school activities. Advisers must prioritize their primary teaching role while effectively organizing and planning their time to accommodate other responsibilities. He stated:

"Do not forget your responsibility as a teacher, balance your task. Kung mahimo magbuhat kag planner." (IDI-06)

(Do not forget your responsibility as a teacher; balance your tasks. If possible, make a planner.)

Research Question No. 4: What insights can the advisers share that may be helpful to other school paper advisers and school administrators?

After speaking with informants, the researcher identified emerging themes: Connecting to Broader Trends, Encouraging Student Participation in Campus Journalism, Prioritizing Skill Development with Collaborative Learning, and Showcasing School Achievement.

Connecting to Broader Trends

Fostering discussions and assignments that encourage students to explore these trends critically and thoughtfully, advisers enable them to develop a deeper understanding of the role of journalism in shaping public discourse. This emphasizes the relevance of staying informed and adapting to evolving media landscapes, preparing students to engage with and contribute meaningfully to contemporary conversations. Bubbly (pseudonym) told the researcher that by experiencing stories firsthand, writers gain a deeper understanding and emotional connection to their narratives, enabling them to convey authenticity, depth, and resonance in their writing. He stated:

"Immerse them, bring them where the story is. Stories become more in-depth, with heart, more telling and with emotions when the writers experience these stories themselves." (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) expressed her feelings by saying that by directly participating in and observing events, students are better equipped to generate diverse ideas and perspectives for their reporting. Such experiential learning enhances students' journalistic skills and encourages critical thinking and creativity as they navigate the complexities of event coverage. He emphasizes:

"Mas daghan ug ideas ang mga bata when they are in the event, so dapat they have firsthand experiences in covering events, with that student can identify different angles and narratives with readers and convey its impact ." (IDI-06)

(Children have more ideas when they are at the event, so they should have firsthand experiences in covering events. With that, students can identify different angles and narratives for readers and convey their impact.)

Encouraging Student Participation in Campus Journalism

School paper advisers highlight their dedication to encouraging student participation in campus journalism as a transformative educational experience. These highlight the significant influence of campus journalism in developing leadership, innovation, and civic involvement among students by creating a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere. Bubbly (pseudonym) stated that effective advertising and enthusiastic student representation can create a compelling narrative that encourages more students to explore and join journalism, enriching their educational experience. He stated:

" Advertise and advertise well. Let your student writers become the walking model of these advertisements. Show the student the benefit of joining journalism." (IDI-05)

It was also supported by Happy (pseudonym), who mentioned that by emphasizing these comprehensive benefits, educators can effectively encourage students to participate in campus journalism, highlighting how it can be both a rewarding and transformative part of their high school journey. He shared:

"Being part of campus journalism provides the students with many benefits, and it not only enriches their experiences in high school but also allows them to learn a lot and improve their ilang skills. That is how I would encourage them to participate or join " (IDI-06)

(Being part of campus journalism provides the students with many benefits because it enriches their experiences in high school and allows them to learn a lot and improve their skills. That is how I would encourage them to participate or join.)

Prioritizing Skill Development with Collaborative Learning

During the interview, it was revealed that advisors stress the importance of group learning in developing aspiring journalists' sense of camaraderie and support for one another and improving their journalistic skills. Bubbly (pseudonym) stated that by integrating collaboration-focused exercises within a training context, students can experience firsthand the synergy and productivity of effective teamwork. He stated:

"Team-building activities can be done but more on training-seminar workshops. Even in these activities, values of collaboration need

to be showcased." (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) also added that exposing students to various learning opportunities such as workshops, seminars, and training sessions allows them to gain valuable knowledge and practical skills. This continuous exposure fosters adaptability and innovation, essential traits in a rapidly changing world. He said:

"Train them well. Nothing beats a trained and open mind. Technology is here to stay so befriend it. Expose them, allow them to attend trainings, workshops, and seminars that could help them grow." (IDI-06)

Showcasing School Achievement

Advisers also emphasize the role of the school paper in enhancing the school's reputation and promoting a positive image both locally and beyond, demonstrating the power of journalism to inform, inspire, and elevate school spirit. Bubbly (pseudonym) shared that by showcasing diverse examples of achievement, the school paper can convey that every student, regardless of their starting point, has the potential to develop and excel through dedication and participation. He emphasized:

"Publish them, write about them. This is the task of the school paper. Announce to the whole school that there are achievements. However, do not end there; we also need to instill the concept of inspiration, that even a simple student can always have their way to continuously develop oneself if s/he continues to be engaged with the activities." (IDI-05)

Moreover, Happy (pseudonym) supported Bubbly by adding that, by documenting and sharing stories, the school paper helps to build a cohesive and supportive school culture where achievements are acknowledged and celebrated, and the community stays informed about important happenings within the school. He confirmed:

"One reason biya why naa tay school paper is to showcase the achievement and highlight the important events happening in the school. So the work of the school paper is to provide stories, interviews, and reports that celebrate their successes and bring wider recognition within the school community." (IDI-06)

(One of the reasons why we have a school paper is to showcase the achievements and highlight the important events happening in the school. So, the work of the school paper is to provide stories, interviews, and reports that celebrate their successes and bring wider recognition within the school community.)

Cross-Case Analysis

Multiple case studies provide an opportunity to examine the best practices of school paper advisers and explore the similarities and differences that occur among individuals. It enables one to look past the specific situation and into the phenomenon. In this example, dealing with the best practices of school paper advisers, a multiple case study supports dealing with the secrets that only the informants can generate in the real life they held. The cases provide an opportunity to investigate by applying the findings from individual case experiences to the study questions and observing occurrences that occur concurrently (Baxter, 2008).

Furthermore, case studies are widely utilized in the social sciences and have proven particularly useful in practice-oriented areas (such as education, management, public administration, and social work). This case study design is a proper way of reflecting the reality that the participants face in their daily lives, allowing for better comprehension of contemporary psychological phenomena. Thus, interviews enable researchers to address the phenomena in depth by giving a platform for informants to describe their experiences in detail, as closely as possible, to reality. It is to grasp the core of the shared experience among participants on a common platform. As a result, participants will express subjective and objective experiences (Mills et al., 2010).

The previous chapter, particularly Chapters 4 to 6, disclosed the best practices of school paper advisers, their live experiences, how they cope with the challenges they encounter, and the insights that they can share with their fellow school paper advisers and school administrators. It also emphasized each informant's different themes and core ideas in each case.

This section presents the differences and similarities of the informants' experiences.

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of advisers in managing school papers?

In the data that the researcher has gathered, and devised five emerging themes: Recognizing and Motivating Students to Development, Prioritizing Open Communication, Encountering Challenges in Forming a Student-Run Paper and Minimizing Adviser Influence on Student Work.

Recognizing and Motivating Students to Development

Teachers not only encourage students to realize their full potential but also create a positive learning environment where development is valued as a continuous process of self-discovery and improvement. They achieve this by fostering a growth mindset and instilling a sense of accomplishment through milestones and feedback loops. Buttercup (pseudonym) reveals that she encourages and support the students efforts by acknowledging their accomplishments, whether it's publishing an engaging piece, conducting an impactful interview, or winning acclaim for their work. This keeps them motivated to continue working in journalism. Acknowledging these successes bolsters their self-esteem and reaffirms their dedication to greatness. She shares:

“Motivating and inspiring students to excel in their journalistic tasks involves recognizing their efforts and achievements while nurturing their passion. I celebrate their successes, whether it's publishing a compelling article, conducting a powerful interview, interview, or receiving recognition for their work.” (IDI-01)

Table 2. *The Lived Experiences of School Paper Adviser*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Recognizing and Motivating Students to Development	Motivating and inspiring students to excel in their journalistic tasks involves recognizing their efforts and achievements while nurturing their passion. I celebrate their successes, whether it is publishing a compelling article, conducting a powerful interview, interview, or receiving recognition for their work. -IDI-01 The kids strive harder when they are recognized, and although they make mistakes and have lapses, that’s how they learn. So, if they create articles that are good, we try to compliment them as much as possible and then provide constructive criticism. – IDI-02 I always ask if they want to see their work in the articles. As an adviser, I use that to ignite the flame inside them and motivate the students. As much as possible, I acknowledge their work and recognize the improvement in their paper. -IDI-03 As a coach, I know how challenging and difficult it is to create articles or even editorial cartoons, so I try to recognize the work of students, whether through awards, publication acknowledgments, or class showcases, to help them build confidence and motivation so they become even more eager to do their work. – IDI-04 To motivate and inspire students, I focus on creating an environment that values each student's contributions and ideas. Celebrating small wins and providing constructive feedback. -IDI-05 Students are motivated to do their work when their work and efforts are recognized. Though they make mistakes, that’s how they learn, so you provide constructive criticism or feedback that does not discourage them. And by the way, food is a good motivator. -IDI-06
Prioritizing Open Communication	As a school paper adviser, I prioritize open communication and collaboration with my students... We establish clear expectations and deadlines, ensuring that everyone knows their responsibilities. – IDI-01 It is really important for the mentor and the student to have good communication so that the mentor is aware of the writer's capabilities and can determine if the task is too difficult or not. We can achieve good outcomes if we communicate. -IDI-02 Work together to advise and balance ideas and responsibilities. There should be open communication between the adviser and the journalist to ensure they are on the same page, so even if they have their own ideas, the teacher can still comment or suggest improvements to make the writing better. -IDI-03 We should also have good communication, because when both of us are communicating, it is more effective and teamwork that could have a positive impact in producing a good output. -IDI-04 Also, talk to students. It is essential that you get to see the context of why the student struggles to write or has a difficulty accomplishing a task. -IDI-05 Open communication creates a more inclusive and collaborative environment. When we communicate with them, we can make flow of ideas, feedback, and discussions that can enhance the quality of the content produced. -IDI-06
Encountering Challenges in Generating Interest and Recruiting Members	One challenge is generating interest and recruiting students to join the publication team... It is also hard building a core team who were not only interested in journalism but also dependable and capable of handling responsibilities was crucial. -IDI-01 One of the challenges a school paper adviser may encounter is establishing a consistent workflow and commitment among students who are balancing multiple academic and extracurricular commitments. -IDI-02 During the initial stages of forming and organizing a student-run school paper, one specific challenge I faced was rallying enough interest and participation from students. -IDI-03 Students think that joining journalism is hard, because it is just for those who are very bright, and that is one of the real challenges in recruiting new members and honing their abilities, because every year you end up training students who will replace those who have graduated. -IDI-04
Minimizing Adviser Influence on Student Work	I prioritize transparency, objectivity, and ethical journalism practices. I encourage students to critically evaluate information, seek diverse perspectives, and adhere to principles of accuracy, fairness, and integrity in their reporting. -IDI-01 To avoid influencing the students' output, the coach should take a hands-off approach while the students are writing. -IDI-02 As I mentioned, give my writers freedom and guide them in the exercise of their freedom. Let them explore their style. Every writer has one. We guide them but we also let them do what they feel like doing. -IDI-05 Allow them to work on their own, with the teacher just guiding from the side. While we share our ideas, it is also important that they are responsible for the output they are writing. -IDI-06

Sharp (pseudonym) seconded and stated that when the adviser acknowledged for the student’s accomplishments, such as creating good articles, they are encouraged to strive harder and take pride in their work. It's important to balance praise with constructive criticism, as this helps them understand their mistakes and learn from them. He said:

“The kids strive harder when they are recognized, and although naa silay mga mistake and lapses but that’s how they learn so kung naa silay mabuhat na artciles which is good, as much as possible we compliment it then provide a constructive criticism.” (IDI-02)

(The kids strive harder when they are recognized, and although they make mistakes and have lapses, that is how they learn. So if they create articles that are good, we try to compliment them as much as possible and then provide constructive criticism.)

Moreover, Brainy (pseudonym) revealed that asking students if they want to see their work in articles is a powerful way for an adviser to ignite their passion and motivation. She stated:

“I always asked og gusto ba nila makita ilang work sa mga articles? So that we can Ignite as an adviser the flame inside saila, I used that para mamotivate ang student. As much as possible I acknowledge their work and recognize the improvement in their paper.” (IDI-03)

(I always ask if they want to see their work in the articles. As an adviser, I use that to ignite the flame inside them and motivate the students. As much as possible, I acknowledge their work and recognize the improvement in their paper.)

Furthermore, Calm (pseudonym) expressed his feelings by sharing that recognizing their efforts through awards, publication acknowledgments, or class showcases, coaches not only validate their hard work but also boost their confidence. She said:

“As a coach, I know unsa ka challenging ug lisod magbuhat ug articles or even sa mga editorial cartooning it is very challenging so I try to recognize the work of students, whether through awards, publication acknowledgments, or class showcases to help them build confidence and motivation na mas maganahan pa sila mu do sailing work.” (IDI-04)

(As a coach, I know how challenging and difficult it is to create articles or even editorial cartoons, so I try to recognize the work of students, whether through awards, publication acknowledgments, or class showcases, to help them build confidence and motivation so they become even more eager to do their work.)

Additionally, Bubbly (pseudonym) articulated that celebrating even small achievements plays a crucial role in boosting their confidence and reinforcing their commitment to learning and growth. He articulated:

“To motivate and inspire students, I focus on creating an environment that values each student's contributions and ideas. Celebrating small wins and providing constructive feedback.” (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) also expressed his feelings by sharing that it is important to acknowledge their successes while understanding that mistakes are part of the learning process, and providing constructive feedback is essential in helping them grow. He said:

“Students are motivated to do their work when their work and efforts are recognized, though they make mistake but that’s how they learn, so you provide constructive criticism or feedback na di maka discourage sa ila. And by the way, food is a good motivation.” (IDI-06)

(Students are motivated to do their work when their work and efforts are recognized. Though they make mistakes, that is how they learn, so you provide constructive criticism or feedback that does not discourage them. And by the way, food is a good motivator.)

Prioritizing Open Communication

Schools establish a welcoming environment where thoughts, worries, and criticism are freely shared and appreciated by promoting open communication among students, teachers, parents, and administrators. This method facilitates efficient problem-solving, fosters respect for one another and builds a sense of community and belonging.

Buttercup (pseudonym) shared that regular communication allows for feedback exchanges and ensures that any challenges or issues can be addressed promptly, thereby maintaining momentum and quality throughout the publication process. She said:

“As a school paper adviser, I prioritize open communication and collaboration with my students... We establish clear expectations and deadlines, ensuring that everyone knows their responsibilities.” (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) supported Buttercup by stressing that effective communication between the mentor and the student is essential to ensure successful mentoring and attaining the desired results. Mentors can better understand the student writer's talents by keeping communication lines open, enabling them to provide projects accordingly. He stated:

“Importante jud na nay good communication si mentor and si student, so that aware si mentor about the capabilities of his writer, to know if the task is too difficult or not. We can achieve good outcomes if we communicate.” (IDI-02)

(It is really important for the mentor and the student to have good communication so that the mentor is aware of the writer's capabilities and can determine if the task is too difficult or not. We can achieve good outcomes if we communicate.)

Furthermore, Brainy (pseudonym) expressed his feelings by sharing that open communication fosters alignment of ideas and responsibilities, ensuring both parties work towards the same goals. She said:

“Work together aron pagtambag og balansehan ang mga ideya ug responsibilidad. There should be an open communication between the adviser and the journalist to ensure na same phase, na even if they have their own idea the teacher can still comment or suggest to make the writing better.” (IDI-03)

(Work together to advise and balance ideas and responsibilities. There should be open communication between the adviser and the journalist to ensure they are on the same page, so even if they have their ideas, the teacher can still comment or suggest improvements to make the writing better.)

Additionally, Calm (pseudonym) articulated that when all team members, whether it is advisers and journalists or any collaborative group, communicate openly and effectively, ideas can be shared, understood, and refined more efficiently. She mentioned:

“We should also have a good communication, kay when both of us are communicating mas effective and teamwork that could have a positive impact in making a good output.” (IDI-04)

(We should also have good communication, because when both of us are communicating, it is more effective and teamwork that could have a positive impact in producing a sound output.)

It was seconded by Bubby (pseudonym). He stated that establishing this open line of communication fosters trust and rapport and empowers students to voice their concerns and seek assistance proactively. He revealed:

“Also, talk to students. It is essential that you get to see the context of why the student struggles to write or has a difficulty accomplishing a task.” (IDI-05)

Moreover, Happy (pseudonym) added that open communication is foundational to creating an inclusive and collaborative environment where ideas flow freely, feedback is constructive. Discussions contribute to the enhancement of content quality. He shared:

“Open communication creates a more inclusive and collaborative environment. When we communicate with them, we can create a flow of ideas, feedback, and discussions that can enhance the quality of the content produced.” (IDI-06)

Challenges of Establishing a Student-Run Newspaper

Overcoming these obstacles fosters a sense of accomplishment and ownership among students, empowering them to develop critical communication, organization, and decision-making skills that are integral to journalism and broader educational experiences. Buttercup (pseudonym) shares that building a core team requires not only finding students interested in journalism but also identifying individuals who are dependable and capable of shouldering responsibilities. She said:

“One challenge is generating interest and recruiting students to join the publication team... It is also hard building a core team who were not only interested in journalism but also dependable and capable of handling responsibilities was crucial.” (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) supported Buttercup by stressing that recognizing and accommodating students' individual strengths and limitations fosters a culture of mutual respect and dedication, essential for sustaining a productive and successful school paper. He mentioned:

“Isa sa challenges a school paper adviser may encounter is also establishing a consistent workflow and commitment among students who were balancing multiple academic and extracurricular commitments.” (IDI-02)

(One of the challenges a school paper adviser may encounter is establishing a consistent workflow and commitment among students who are balancing multiple academic and extracurricular commitments.)

Furthermore, Brainy (pseudonym) expressed his feelings by sharing that getting enough students interested in and involved in a school newspaper during its founding and early phases was a significant problem. In order to successfully complete this work, the paper's goals and advantages had to be effectively promoted, with a focus on chances for creativity, skill improvement, and community influence. She shared:

“During the initial stages sa pag-buo ug pag-organize sa school-run school paper, isa ka specific challenge na akong gi atubang kay ang pag himok mismo sa interest ug participation sa students”. (IDI- 03)

(During the initial stages of forming and organizing a student-run school paper, one specific challenge I faced was rallying enough interest and participation from students.)

Additionally, Calm (pseudonym) articulated that for school paper advisers, establishing a consistent process and dedication from students juggling multiple extracurricular and academic commitments is a big issue. This problem emphasizes how adaptable scheduling and efficient time management techniques are necessary to meet the varied schedules of pupils. She revealed:

“Students think that joining journalism is hard, kay para rana sya sa mga bright bright, and that is one of the challenges gyod ang pag recruit ug new members and honing their abilities, kay every year mag train naman sad kag mga studyane na mupuli sa mga nang graduate.” (IDI-04)

(Students think that joining journalism is hard, because it is just for those who are very bright, and that is one of the real challenges in recruiting new members and honing their abilities, because every year you end up training students who will replace those who have graduated.)

Minimizing Adviser Influence on Student Work

The value of advisers acting as mentors rather than controllers, offering advice and experience while letting students exercise their own judgment and express their creativity. By encouraging children to explore their own voices, viewpoints, and creative impulses, this method helps them develop a sense of pride in their work and ownership over it. Advisors help students develop professional responsibility, ethical judgment, and critical thinking skills by limiting direct influence. This helps students get ready for future undertakings where independence and self-direction are crucial.

Buttercup (pseudonym) has stated that by highlighting the significance of critically assessing data and pursuing varied viewpoints, instructors motivate learners to approach their assignments with a dedication to accuracy and proportionality. She stated:

“I prioritize transparency, objectivity, and ethical journalism practices. I encourage students to critically evaluate information, seek diverse perspectives, and adhere to principles of accuracy, fairness, and integrity in their reporting.” (IDI-01)

It was seconded by Sharp (pseudonym). He stated that refraining from direct influence, coaches allow students the freedom to explore their own voices, perspectives, and storytelling styles. He shared:

“To avoid influencing the students output no, the coach should hands-off approach during or while ga write ang students.” (IDI-02)

(To avoid influencing the students' output, the coach should take a hands-off approach while the students are writing.)

Moreover, Bubbly (pseudonym) added that by balancing guidance with freedom, coaches ensure that students learn to uphold journalistic principles while embracing creativity, allowing them to produce compelling and impactful content that reflects their diverse perspectives and talents. He mentioned:

“As I mentioned, give my writers freedom and guide them in the exercise of their freedom. Let them explore their style. Every writer has one. We guide them but we also let them do what they feel like doing.” (IDI-05)

Happy pseudonym) also expressed his feelings by sharing that students can learn how to overcome obstacles, express their creativity, and create meaningful journalism that represents their unique perspectives and personal development in a supportive learning atmosphere that is fostered by a collaborative yet student-centered approach. He said:

“Allow them to work on their own, guide on the side lang bya si teacher. While we share our ideas, it is also important that they are responsible on the output that they are writing.” (IDI-06)

(Allow them to work on their own, with the teacher just guiding from the side. While we share our ideas, it is also important that they are responsible for the output they are writing.)

Research Question No. 3: How do advisers cope up with the challenges they face with regards to handling school paper organization?

After conversing with the informants, the researcher established four emerging themes: Fostering Adviser’s Development, Balancing Workload, Adhering to Resource Management, and Fostering Students Development in Journalism.

Table 3. *How Advisers Overcome Challenges in Managing the School Paper Organization*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Commitment to Continuous Professional Growth for Effective Journalism Advising	Improving my own journalistic knowledge and skills is essential for effectively advising the school paper and staying current with the trends. I engage in continuous professional development through reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars. -IDI-01
	Engage in continuous professional development through reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars. -IDI-02
Balancing Workload	I strive to expand my knowledge base and refine my craft as an adviser, I attend workshops, conference, seminar related to journalism. Through these efforts, I ensure that I am well-equipped to support and mentor students effectively in their journalistic pursuits. -IDI-03
	Regularly participate in workshop trainings to improve and actively seeking opportunities for learning and growth, with this I can enhance my ability to support and inspire student journalists. -IDI-04
	Balancing teaching workloads and advising the school paper requires effective time management, communication, and collaboration. -IDI-01
	Organize a planner, being a mentor and a teacher can be both challenging so it is important to have good time management. IDI-02
	I allocate specific blocks of time for both teaching and advising duties, ensuring that each aspect receives adequate attention. -IDI-03
	Balance your responsibility because you are not just an adviser to the school paper, you are also a teacher. You should have good time management. -IDI-04
	It is all about time management. I make sure that I do first my job as a teacher and then devote a time for my school paper adviser work. -IDI-05
	Do not forget your responsibility as a teacher, balance your tasks. If possible, make a planner. -IDI-06

Practicing Effective Resource Management	<p>I work closely with school administrators and parent-teacher association to advocate for funding and resources especially during general assembly and special meetings. -IDI-01</p> <p>School papers have a huge contribution in the school and securing financial and administrative support for the school paper involves building relationships with key stakeholders and demonstrating the publication's value to the school community. -IDI-02</p> <p>I need to present a clear and good plan for using funds and resources. I also highlight the benefits and value that the school paper brings to the institution, emphasizing its role in student development and community engagement. -IDI-03</p> <p>Through the support of the school's stakeholders, like ang PTA. We can secure funds for the school paper. -IDI-04</p>
Fostering Students Development in Journalism by Enhancing Skill	<p>I can help students improve their journalistic skills and knowledge by providing hands-on training and practical experiences in news writing, interviewing techniques, and research methods. -IDI-03</p> <p>Helping students improve their journalistic skills and knowledge involves a combination of hands-on experience, mentorship, and structured learning opportunities. I provide ongoing feedback and guidance on their writing, reporting, and storytelling techniques, emphasizing the importance of accuracy, fairness, and ethical conduct. -IDI-04</p> <p>Encourage students to pursue and attend journalism conferences and participate in competitions like press conferences to develop their skills further and expand their networks. -IDI-05</p> <p>Expose the students to winning papers, video tutorials, and seminars in journalism. IDI-06</p>

Adviser's Commitment to Continuous Professional Growth for Effective Journalism Advising

Encouraging the growth of advisers in journalism and other educational jobs is essential to guarantee their efficacy and longevity. By encouraging innovation and excellence in journalism education, advisor development investments improve advisers' capacity to coach and lead students successfully and fortify the educational community. Additionally, encouraging a reflective practice where advisers can learn from experiences and adapt their approaches fosters a culture of continuous improvement.

Buttercup (pseudonym) stated that engaging in continuous professional development, such as reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars, ensures that one remains well-informed and equipped to guide the school paper's editorial direction.

"Improving my own journalistic knowledge and skills is essential for effectively advising the school paper and staying current with the trends. I engage in continuous professional development through reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars." (IDI-01)

In addition, Sharp (pseudonym) added that by actively participating in these activities that relate to continuous professional development, individuals improve their capabilities and contribute to the overall growth and innovation within their respective fields, ultimately fostering personal and professional development. He stated:

"Engage in continuous professional development through reading publications, attending conferences, and participating in workshops and webinars." (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Brainy (pseudonym) shared that workshops provide opportunities to stay updated with evolving industry practices, learn new methodologies, and gain insights into emerging trends, enhancing the ability to support and mentor students in their journalistic endeavors. She shared:

"I strive to expand my knowledge base and refine my craft as an adviser; I attend workshops, conferences, and seminars related to journalism. Through these efforts, I ensure that I am well-equipped to support and mentor students effectively in their journalistic pursuits." (IDI-03)

It was also supported by Bubby (pseudonym), who stated that individuals can acquire new skills, stay updated with industry advancements, and gain fresh perspectives that enrich their mentorship approach through participating in workshop trainings and actively seeking opportunities for learning and growth. She said:

"Regularly participate in workshop training to improve and actively seek opportunities for learning and growth, with this I can enhance my ability to support and inspire student journalists." (IDI-04)

Balancing Workload

Managing various responsibilities such as lesson planning, grading, student support, and professional development while maintaining a healthy work-life balance is difficult. Encouraging efficient time management, providing support systems, and promoting self-care strategies help both educators and students navigate their workload effectively, fostering a productive and fulfilling learning environment for all involved.

Buttercup (pseudonym) shares that balancing teaching responsibilities with advising the school paper demands adept time management, clear communication, and collaborative skills. She stated:

“Balancing teaching workloads and advising the school paper requires effective time management, communication, and collaboration.” (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also agreed with Buttercup, saying that a well-structured planner helps maintain focus, ensures deadlines are met, and allows for adequate preparation and reflection time, thereby maximizing productivity and fostering a supportive environment for student development. He mentioned:

“Organize a planner, being a mentor and a teacher can be both challenging so it is important to have good time management.” (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Brainy (pseudonym) also told the researcher that by dedicating focused periods to teaching, educators can engage with students effectively, deliver comprehensive lessons, and provide timely feedback on assignments. She emphasized:

“I allocate specific blocks of time for both teaching and advising duties, ensuring that each aspect receives adequate attention.” (IDI-03)

Additionally, Calm (pseudonym) added that recognizing that these roles require different types of engagement and commitment, effective time allocation ensures that each aspect receives the necessary attention without neglecting either. She stated:

“Balance your responsibility kay dili man ka adviser lang sa school paper, you are also a teacher. Dapat nakay time management.” (IDI-04)

(Balance your responsibility because you are not just an adviser to the school paper, you are also a teacher. You should have good time management.)

It was also supported by Bubby (pseudonym), who stated that teachers may guarantee they satisfy curricular requirements, provide high-quality education, and foster students' academic success by putting their teaching responsibilities first. After completing these fundamental tasks, setting out time for school newspaper advising enables students to receive excellent mentoring, editorial direction, and training in journalism. He shared:

“It is all about time management. I make sure that I do first my job as a teacher and then devote time for my school paper adviser work.” (IDI-05)

Lastly, Happy (pseudonym) shared the same thought with Bubby that advisers can make sure they carry out their teaching responsibilities with diligence and give their advisory work enough time and attention by following a set timetable. This methodical approach not only boosts output but also fosters professional development and makes it possible for teachers to offer students invaluable help and direction both within and outside of the classroom. He emphasized:

“Do not forget your responsibility as a teacher, balance your task. Kung mahimo magbuhat kag planner.” (IDI-06)

(Do not forget your responsibility as a teacher, balance your tasks. If possible, make a planner.)

Practicing Effective Resource Management

Resource management, which emphasizes the effective and ethical distribution of resources including time, money, and materials, is essential to both journalism and education. This means that in educational settings, lesson design should be optimized, technology should be used wisely, and instructional aids should be used to maximize learning outcomes and reduce waste. Buttercup (pseudonym) revealed that:

“I work closely with school administrators and parent-teacher association to advocate for funding and resources, especially during general assembly and special meetings.” (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also suggested that securing financial and administrative support for the school paper requires building strong relationships with key stakeholders, such as school administrators, teachers, parents, and local businesses. He stated:

“School papers have a huge contribution in the school and securing financial and administrative support for the school paper involves building relationships with key stakeholders and demonstrating the publication's value to the school community.” (IDI-02)

Additionally, Brainy (pseudonym) stated that receiving assistance for the school paper requires presenting a well-organized and transparent plan for using funds and resources. This strategy should specify how funds will be distributed to improve the publication's quality and audience while maintaining accountability and openness. She shared:

“Kinahanglan nako nga magpakita og klaro ug maayong plano sa paggamit sa pondo ug mga resources. I also highlight the benefits and value that the school paper brings to the institution, emphasizing its role in student development and community engagement.” (IDI-03)

(Through the support of the school's stakeholders, like ang PTA. We can secure funds for the school paper.)

In addition, Calm (pseudonym) affirmed with Bubby, saying that stakeholders are more likely to contribute to the school newspaper's

ongoing operations when it is shown to provide measurable benefits, such as enhanced literacy, critical thinking, and a sense of community. She confirmed:

“Through the support of the school's stakeholders, like ang PTA. We can secure funds for the school paper.” (IDI-04)

Fostering Students' Development in Journalism

Teachers are essential in helping students understand the concepts of critical thinking, ethical reporting, and research techniques. By giving students opportunities to gain practical experience in writing, editing, and multimedia production, teachers enable students to hone their journalistic voices and explore new interests. Brainy (pseudonym) shares that through direct instruction and real-world practice, students gain a deeper understanding of how to craft compelling news stories, conduct effective and insightful interviews, and perform thorough research. She said:

“I can help students improve their journalistic skills and knowledge by providing hands-on training and practical experiences in news writing.” (IDI-03)

Calm (pseudonym) also agreed with Brainy, saying that mentorship is crucial, as ongoing feedback and personalized guidance help students refine their writing, reporting, and storytelling techniques. Emphasizing the principles of accuracy, fairness, and ethical conduct ensures that students develop technical skills and understand the responsibilities and standards of professional journalism. She shared:

“Helping students improve their journalistic skills and knowledge involves a combination of hands-on experience, mentorship, and structured learning opportunities. I provide ongoing feedback and guidance on their writing, reporting, and storytelling techniques, emphasizing the importance of accuracy, fairness, and ethical conduct.” (IDI-04)

Furthermore, Bubbly (pseudonym) also told the researcher that encouraging students to attend journalism conferences and participate in competitions, such as press conferences, is essential for their professional growth and skill development. These opportunities expose students to the latest industry trends, innovative practices, and diverse perspectives, broadening their understanding of journalism. He said:

“Also encourage students to pursue and attend journalism conferences, and participate in competitions like press conferences to further develop their skills and expand their networks.” (IDI-05)

Finally, Happy (pseudonym) added that attending seminars allows students to engage with experts, stay updated on industry trends, and gain inspiration. This comprehensive exposure cultivates their critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability, equipping them with the knowledge and skills needed to excel in journalism. He stated:

“Expose the students to winning papers, international papers, video tutorials and attend seminars in journalism.” (IDI-06)

Research Question No. 4: What insights can the advisers share that may be helpful to other school paper advisers and school administrators?

After conversing with the informants, the researcher established three emerging themes: Connecting to Broader Trends, Showcasing School Achievements, and Encouraging Student Participation in Campus Journalism.

Connecting to Broader Trends

All three cases admitted that they all connect broader trends. To prepare students to navigate and contribute to a changing world, educators must incorporate current events and new trends into the curriculum. By increasing the learning experience's relevance to real-world situations, this link promotes critical thinking and flexibility. Both educators and journalists may better serve the needs and interests of their audiences by integrating their methods with broader trends, which will promote advancement and innovation in their respective industries.

Table 4. *The Insights of School Paper Advisers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Connecting to Broader Trends	I encourage students to seek out interesting stories within the school community and explore the diverse interests and activities of their peers, highlighting the advocacy not just reporting an event. -IDI-01 Encourage students to observe their surroundings, ask questions, and listen to the stories of their peers. -IDI-02 I empower student journalists by encouraging them to immerse themselves in their communities, listening attentively to the narratives unfolding around them. By fostering curiosity and empathy, students can uncover compelling story ideas rooted in the experiences and challenges of their peers. -ID-03 Encourage students to explore different storytelling formats and approaches, such as human-interest features, investigative reports, or opinion pieces, to find the most engaging and impactful way to tell their stories. ... through compelling storytelling and vivid imagery, these achievements can be brought to life, resonating with readers. -IDI-04 Immerse them, bring them where the story is. Stories become more in-depth, with heart, more telling and with emotions when the writers experience these stories themselves. -IDI-05 Children have more ideas when they are at the event, so they should have firsthand experiences in covering events.

Showcasing School Achievements	<p>With that, students can identify different angles and narratives for readers and convey it is impact. -IDI-06</p> <p>Additionally, I highlight success stories and achievements of past and current student journalists, demonstrating the impact and recognition they have received within the school community and beyond. -IDI-01</p> <p>Journalism can be used to highlight the achievements and initiatives of different clubs, teams, and programs by showcasing their stories in a compelling and engaging manner. -IDI-02</p> <p>Journalism serves as a powerful tool in spotlighting the accomplishments and endeavors of various clubs, teams, and programs within a school community. By weaving narratives that capture the essence of their efforts, journalists can effectively convey the passion and dedication behind each endeavor. -IDI-03</p> <p>The school paper makes a big contribution in telling stories, especially when there are events, as they capture moments. -IDI-04</p> <p>Publish them, write about them. This is the task of the school paper. Announce to the whole school that there are achievements. But do not end there; we need to also instill the concept of inspiration, that even a simple student can always have their way to continuously develop oneself if s/he continues to be engaged with the activities. -IDI-05</p> <p>One of the reasons why we have a school paper is to showcase the achievements and highlight the important events happening in the school. So, the work of the school paper is to provide stories, interviews, and reports that celebrate their successes and bring wider recognition within the school community. -IDI-06</p>
Encouraging Student Participation in Campus Journalism	<p>To encourage students to join the campus paper, it is vital to highlight the benefits of participation, such as honing writing skills, gaining journalistic experience, and contributing to the school community. Hosting workshops and seminars on journalism basics can pique interest and guide aspiring writers. -IDI-03</p> <p>Helping the school to encourage students to join the campus paper involves promoting the benefits and opportunities of participating in student journalism. -IDI-04</p> <p>Advertise and advertise well. Let your student writers become the walking model of these advertisements. Show the student the good benefits of joining journalism. IDI-05</p> <p>Being part of campus journalism provides the students with a lot of benefits, because it not only enriches their experiences in high school but also allows them to learn a lot and improve their skills. That is how I would encourage them to participate or join. -IDI-06</p>

Buttercup (pseudonym) stated that encouraging students to seek out interesting stories within the school community goes beyond merely reporting events; it fosters advocacy by delving into the diverse interests and activities of their peers. She said:

“I encourage students to seek out interesting stories within the school community and explore the diverse interests and activities of their peers, highlighting the advocacy not just reporting an event.” (IDI-01)

In addition, Sharp (pseudonym) added that promoting active engagement with their environment and peers, students develop valuable skills in communication and empathy, learning to appreciate diverse perspectives and experiences. He stated:

“Encourage students to observe their surroundings, ask questions, and listen to the stories of their peers.” (IDI-02)

Brainy (pseudonym) seconded the statement by saying that through immersion in their communities, students learn to amplify voices that might otherwise be overlooked, contributing to a richer and more inclusive portrayal of their school environment and beyond. She shared:

“I empower student journalists by encouraging them to immerse themselves in their communities, listening attentively to the narratives unfolding around them. By fostering curiosity and empathy, students can uncover compelling story ideas rooted in the experiences and challenges of their peers.” (IDI-03)

Furthermore, Calm (pseudonym) shared that by experimenting with different formats, students enhance their creativity and writing skills and learn to tailor their narratives to captivate and resonate with readers. When students explore human-interest features, investigative reports, or opinion pieces, they learn to see stories from multiple angles and recognize the nuances within each subject. Blending these varied storytelling techniques with vivid imagery, students can transform everyday achievements into compelling narratives that inspire, inform, and connect with the audience on a personal level. She mentioned:

“Encourage students to explore different storytelling formats and approaches, such as human-interest features, investigative reports, or opinion pieces, to find the most engaging and impactful way to tell their stories. ... through compelling storytelling and vivid imagery, these achievements can be brought to life, resonating with readers.” (IDI-04)

It was also supported by Bubby (pseudonym), who stated that Immersing student writers directly in the environments where stories unfold enrich their narratives with depth, heart, and emotional resonance. When writers immerse themselves fully in the stories they cover, they gain a firsthand perspective that goes far beyond mere observation. This experience allows them to capture details, emotions, and nuances that cannot be conveyed from a distance. He said:

“Immerse them, bring them where the story is. Stories become more in-depth, with heart, more telling and with emotions when the writers experience these stories themselves.” (IDI-05)

Moreover, Happy (pseudonym) shared the same thought with Bubby, which is that firsthand experience allows them to gather authentic details and emotions and fosters a deeper understanding of the event's significance. It empowers students to convey the atmosphere,

stories, and implications of the event more convincingly, enriching their storytelling and journalistic skills while providing readers with more insightful and engaging content. He shared:

“Mas daghan ug ideas ang mga bata when they are in the event, so dapat they have firsthand experiences in covering events, with that student can identify different angles and narratives with readers and convey its impact.” (IDI-06)

(Children have more ideas when they are at the event, so they should have firsthand experiences in covering events. With that, students can identify different angles and narratives for readers and convey their impact.)

Showcasing School Achievement

Schools may promote an environment that inspires and encourages continuous excellence by recognizing and honoring noteworthy projects, extracurricular successes, and academic achievements. In addition to raising spirits, this approach enhances the school's reputation, drawing in prospective students and gaining the community's and alums's support. Various channels, including school websites, newsletters, social media, and local media outlets, can effectively showcase work, guaranteeing that accomplishments are acknowledged and appreciated.

For Buttercup (pseudonym), showcasing these success stories, such as awards won, impactful articles published, or community recognition received, prospective student journalists can see the tangible outcomes and recognition their peers have achieved through their involvement. She said:

"Additionally, I highlight success stories and achievements of past and current student journalists, demonstrating the impact and recognition they have received within the school community and beyond." (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also agreed with Buttercup, saying that by presenting these narratives compellingly and engagingly, journalism not only celebrates the successes and efforts of these groups but also promotes a sense of community pride and recognition. He stated:

"Journalism can be used to highlight the achievements and initiatives of different clubs, teams, and programs by showcasing their stories in a compelling and engaging manner." (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Brainy (pseudonym) also told the researcher that journalism is a potent tool for spotlighting the accomplishments and endeavors of clubs, teams, and programs within a school community. She mentioned:

"Journalism is a powerful tool in spotlighting the accomplishments and endeavors of various clubs, teams, and programs within a school community. By weaving narratives that capture the essence of their efforts, journalists can effectively convey the passion and dedication behind each endeavor." (IDI-03)

Calm (pseudonym) added that through detailed reporting and thoughtful analysis, the school paper not only documents events but also provides context, highlighting the impact and significance of these moments on students, faculty, and the broader school environment. The school paper does more than report on events. It serves as the school's collective memory, preserving moments that might otherwise fade. Each article, photo, and story holds the power to reflect the unique character and spirit of the student body, creating a lasting narrative that future students, faculty, and even alums can look back on. She revealed:

“Dako bya ug contribution ang school paper in telling the stories, especially pag nay mga events they capture moments.” (IDI-04)

(The school paper makes a significant contribution in telling stories, especially when there are events, as they capture moments.)

Additionally, Bubbly (pseudonym) stated that the role of the school paper extends beyond merely publishing achievements to encompass inspiring and motivating the entire school community. Beyond merely announcing achievements, a school paper holds the potential to shape a culture of inspiration and growth. Showcasing student stories, talents, and personal journeys, the paper can highlight the outcome of hard work and the journey of dedication and resilience that leads to those achievements. She said:

“Publish them, write about them. This is the task of the school paper. Announce to the whole school that there are achievements. However, don't end there, we need to also instill the concept of inspiration; that even a simple student can always have their way to continuously develop oneself if s/he continues to be engaged with the activities.” (IDI-05)

Happy (pseudonym) affirmed with Bubbly, saying that providing stories, interviews, and reports that celebrate successes, the paper not only informs students and staff about noteworthy accomplishments but also fosters a sense of pride and unity. Through its coverage, the paper amplifies the impact of these achievements, promoting recognition and appreciation among peers and administrators alike. He confirmed:

“One of the reason biya why naa tay school paper is to showcase the achievement and highlight the important events happening in the school. So the work of the school paper is to provide stories, interviews, and reports that celebrate their successes and bring wider recognition within the school community.” (IDI-06)

(One of the reasons why we have a school paper is to showcase the achievements and highlight the important events happening in the school. So, the work of the school paper is to provide stories, interviews, and reports that celebrate their successes and bring wider

recognition within the school community.)

Encouraging Students' Participation in Journalism

Participating in campus journalism fosters a more vibrant, welcoming school climate where various viewpoints are acknowledged and respected. Additionally, providing students with practical experience and a grasp of journalistic ethics prepares them for future careers in media and communications. In the end, encouraging student participation in journalism enhances the educational process and allows students to make significant contributions to their community and school. Buttercup (pseudonym) revealed that hosting workshops and seminars that cover journalism basics ignites interest and offers aspiring writers essential guidance and practical knowledge to get started.

"To encourage students to join the campus paper, it is vital to highlight the benefits of participation, such as honing writing skills, gaining journalistic experience, and contributing to the school community. Hosting workshops and seminars on journalism basics can pique interest and provide guidance for aspiring writers." (IDI-01)

Sharp (pseudonym) also suggested that highlighting opportunities to engage with the school community, cover important events, and amplify diverse voices helps students understand the impact they can have through their writing. He said:

"Helping the school to encourage students to join the campus paper involves promoting the benefits and opportunities of participating in student journalism." (IDI-02)

Brainy (pseudonym) also stated that effectively advertising the benefits of joining journalism involves showcasing student writers as examples of those benefits. She shared:

"Advertise and advertise well. Let your student writers become the walking model of these advertisements. Show to the student the good benefit of joining journalism." (IDI-03)

Finally, Calm (pseudonym) affirmed with Brainy that being part of campus journalism offers students numerous benefits that enrich their high school experiences and facilitate significant skill development. Students gain opportunities to hone their writing, communication, and critical thinking skills in a real-world context by participating. She confirmed:

"Being part of campus journalism provides the students with a lot of benefits, and it not only enriches their experiences in high school but also allows them to learn a lot and improve their writing skills. That's how, I would encourage them to participate or join." (IDI-04)

(Being part of campus journalism provides the students with a lot of benefits, because it not only enriches their experiences in high school but also allows them to learn a lot and improve their skills. That is how I would encourage them to participate or join.)

Conclusions

The result of the analysis of this multiple-case study allowed the researcher to examine and understand the best practices of school paper adviser, their lived experiences, how they cope with the challenges they encounter in handling school paper organization, and the insights that they can share to other school paper adviser and school administrators. Now, it is crucial to consider the implications of improving the practices and the need for school paper advisers to handle school paper organization. As the researcher of this study, I allowed them to share their best practices and perspectives on how they will be able to deal with the challenges they might face. The researcher considers their strategies would be strengthened by my relevant, valid, and balanced methodologies, which would benefit their morale as school paper advisers.

In addition, I was responsible for treating them with respect, conducting the research more seriously, and taking good care of the private information they provided as a valuable source of information for the study. Furthermore, this research gave me ideas for handling an organization that addresses issues such as lack of leadership in an organization like a school paper.

For school paper advisers, the research is essential since it provides different ideas on how they use various practices in handling school papers. They may use the practices to enrich their strategies. Moreover, they may consider the suggestions and advice shared by the participants in this study.

Along with this, the study would be a basis on which higher body institutions like the Commission on Higher Education might make and implement seminar workshops to assist the school paper adviser in their strategy for handling school papers. They may also assist with training programs, materials, and additional technology to help them better implement their practices. Also, the Department of Education school paper advisers and school administrators would benefit from the study's findings. The study identifies various practices and strategies that may help inform the development of evidence-based methods in school paper organization.

Lastly, to future researchers who are interested in conducting a study related to the best practices of school paper advisers, this study would somehow assist them in gathering information that will be needed in their study, and they can use the result, review related literature, and methodology as their references in completing their research paper.

Implications for Further Research

The result of the analysis of this multiple-case study was only able to explore the practices of school paper advisers. It only explores how school paper advisers cope with the challenges they have encountered in handling school paper organization and the insights they can share with other school paper advisers and administrators. The study failed to explore the effect of the adviser's beliefs and attitudes towards journalism and how these can impact their practices in handling a school paper organization.

By this, the researcher wants the future researcher to conduct a study that explores the effect of advisers' beliefs and attitudes towards journalism and how these can impact their practices in handling a school paper organization. They could explore how advisers' beliefs about journalism, confidence in avoiding bias, and perceptions of student abilities influence their practices. This line of inquiry could inform professional development initiatives and help address potential barriers to effective practices.

References

- Advincula, A., & Adtoon, J. (2024). Narratives of Campus Publication. Retrieved November 2, 2024, from https://www.feu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/4_Narratives-of-Campus-Publication-Advisers.pdf
- Aspers, P. & Corte, U. (2019). What is Qualitative in Qualitative Research. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-019-9413-7>
- Astin, A. W. (1984). Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education. *Journal of College Student Personnel*,
- Asrar, Z., Tariq, N., & Rashid, H. (2018). The Impact of Communication Between Teachers and Students: A Case Study of the Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Karachi, Pakistan. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 14(16), 32. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2018.v14n16p32>
- Bañez, R. & Latido, R. (2018). Examining the Management of Human Resources in Campus-Based Student Publication. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*
- Barberos, m. T., Gozalo, a., & Padayogdog, E. (2019). The Effect of the Teacher's Teaching Style on Students' Motivation. NYU Steinhardt. <https://steinhardt.nyu.edu/departments/teaching-and-learning/research/practitioner-action-research/effect-teachers-teaching>
- Barchas-Lichtenstein, J., Voiklis, J., Glasser, D. B., & Fraser, J. (2021). Finding relevance in the news: The scale of self-reference. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 171, 49–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2020.10.001>
- Burelison, A. H., Rust, M. M. ., Chaille, M. E., Huff, A. F., Crist, M., & Klosterman, G. (2021). Help us, help students: supporting advisors during COVID-19. *Journal of the Student Personnel Association at Indiana University*, 98-107. <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/jiuspa/article/view/32524>
- Bhandari, P. (2022). Ethical Considerations in Research | Types & Examples. Scriber. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research-ethics/>
- Bliven, A. (2021). The Impact of Student Recognition of Excellence to Student Outcome in a Competency-Based Educational Model. (2021, June 15). *The EvoLLLution*. <https://evolllution.com/attracting-students/retention/the-impact-of-student-recognition-of-excellence-to-student-outcome-in-a-competency-based-educational-model>
- Calub, C. (2023). CAMPUS JOURNALISM AND CHALLENGES FACED BY STUDENT JOURNALISTS - AN OVERVIEW.
- Cubillas, A. & Cubillas, T. (2021). Awareness and Compliance with Campus Journalism of the Public and Private Elementary Schools: Basis for Crafting a Campus Journalism Implementation Teachers' Training. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*
- Chatterjee, N. (2021, November 16). Influence Of Teachers On Students: How and Why? *Codevidhya*. <https://codevidhya.com/influence-teachers-students/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAAR0RE88aifSB20r7KIBm>
- Chavez, J. V., Anuddin, F. O., Mansul, H. H., Hawari, N. A., Irilis, F. B., Umaron, A. A., Kaslani, F. A. L., Matugol, F. S.-R. B., Siring, R. M., Albani, S. E., Chavez, J. V., Anuddin, F. O., Mansul, H. H., Hawari, N. A., Irilis, F. B., Umaron, A. A., Kaslani, F. A. L., Matugol, F. S.-R. B., Siring, R. M., & Albani, S. E. (2024). Analyzing impacts of campus journalism on student's grammar consciousness and confidence in writing engagements. *Environment and Social Psychology*, 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.59429/esp.v9i7.6106>
- Chen, T.-M. (2019). A Promising Connection of College Journalism Students and Community Engagement. *Higher Education Studies*, 10(1), 60. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v10n1p60>
- Creswell, J. W. & Miller, D. L. (2000). Determining Validity in Qualitative Inquiry https://people.ucsc.edu/~ktellez/Creswell_validity2000.pdf
- Cresswell, J. W. (2009). A phenomenological study of millennial generation cooperative extension educators' development of core competencies. University of Nebraska - Lincoln DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln.
- Cresswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed). SAGE Publications, Inc.

<https://nbnresolving.de/urn:de:0114-fqs1502256>

Dela Rosa, J., Lucero, N. & Vargas, D. (2021). *CAMPUS JOURNALISM: VARYING CULTURES AND ITS EFFECTS TO SECONDARY CAMPUS JOURNALISTS*. Elsevier.

Deloria, G. R., Eslabon, R., & Eslabon, L. (2024). Preparedness and Coaching Styles of the School Paper Advisers on Campus Journalism in the New Normal. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(6), 621–634. <https://risejournals.org/index.php/imjrise/article/view/503/751>

Demas, J. (2018). *The Road to Tenure: Obstacles for the Media Adviser*. Digital Commons

Diaz, D., Farruggia, S. P., Wellman, M. E., & Bottoms, B. L. (2019). Honors education 94 has a positive effect on college student success. *Journal of the National Collegiate Honors Council*.

Diop, Layire. (2023). *Open Access Mass Communication & Journalism*.

Dicke, Theresa & Marsh, Herb & Parker, Philip & Pekrun, Reinhard & Guo, Jiesi & Televantou, Ioulia. (2018). Effects of School-Average Achievement on Individual Self-Concept and Achievement: Unmasking Phantom Effects Masquerading as True Compositional Effects. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 110. 10.1037/edu0000259

Dorow, N. (2019). *Fostering Student Interest and Motivation in Second Grade Writing*. https://digitalcommons.hamline.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1404&context=hse_cp

Drok, N. (2018). Towards a Broader Concept of Innovation in Journalism. *Questions de Communication*, 34, 271–284. <https://doi.org/10.4000/questionsdecommunication.15999>

Dye, T. (2021). *Qualitative data analysis: Step-by-step guide (manual vs. automatic) | thematic*. <https://getthematic.com/insights/qualitative-data-analysis/amp>

Edilberto, H., & Jr. (2019). Lived Experiences of School Paper Advisers in Secondary Campus Journalism: A Phenomenological Approach. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2F). <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/8812>

Farrugia, L. (2019). WASP (Write a Scientific Paper): The ongoing process of ethical decision-making in qualitative research: Ethical principles and their application to the research process. *Early Human Development*, 133, 48–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2019.03.011>

Gustafsson, J. (2017). *Single case studies vs. multiple case studies: A comparative study*. Case Study, Single Case Study, Multiple Case Studies. Published.

Gul, Rani & Tahir, Dr & Batool, Tayyaba. (2021). Impact of Teachers' Workload on Their Time Management Skills at University Level. *Indian Journal of Economics and Business*. 20. 819-829.

Heale, R., & Twycross, A. (2017). What is a case study? *Evidence Based Nursing*, 21(1), 7–8. doi:10.1136/eb-2017-102845

Hettinga, K. (2018). Exploring how college media advisers teach accuracy: Putting accuracy education theory into practice. *College Media Review | Journal of the College Media Association*.

Hite, R., & Taylor, D. (2021). Fostering Interest in and Motivation for STEM: An Illustrative Case Study of Middle Grade Students' Experiences in Out of School (OST) STEM Activities. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Teacher Leadership*. <https://doi.org/10.46767/kfp.2016-0035>

Ismail, Awan & Ismail, Rizalawati. (2018). Knowledge versus Experience: Indicator to Good Journalism Practices. *Jurnal Komunikasi, Malaysian Journal of Communication*. 33. 142-158. 10.17576/JKMJC-2017-3304-09.

Johnson, J. S., Adkins, D., & Chauvin, S. W. (2019). A Review of the Quality Indicators of Rigor in Qualitative Research. *The American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 84(1), 7120. <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe7120>

Kalu, F. A., & Bwalya, J. C. (2017). What Makes Qualitative Research Good Research? An Exploratory Analysis of Critical Elements. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 5(2), 43-56. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijssr.v5i2.10711>

Kanwal, Ayesha & Rafiq, Shahid & Afzal, Dr. (2023). Impact of Workload on Teachers' Efficiency and Their Students' Academic Achievement at the University Level. 39. 131-146. 10.51380/gujr-39-02-02.

Keith, R. (2020). *The Charger: A Case Study of Leadership Decisions and the Oxford High School Student Newspaper*. ProQuest

Kumar, H. (2023). *Building a Solid Foundation: Outlining in Fiction Writing*. (n.d.). [www.linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/building-solid-foundation-importance-outlining-fiction-k-hari-kumar?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNh). Retrieved June 17, 2024, from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/building-solid-foundation-importance-outlining-fiction-k-hari-kumar?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNh>

- Klykken, F. H. (2021). Implementing continuous consent in qualitative research. *Qualitative Research*, 146879412110143. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14687941211014366>
- Kyngas, H., Kaariainen, M., & Elo, S. (2020). The Trustworthiness of Content Analysis. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336965902_The_Trustworthiness_of_Content_Analysis
- Kramp, L., & Loosen, W. (2018). The Transformation of Journalism: From Changing Newsroom Cultures to a New Communicative Orientation? *Communicative Figurations*, 205–239. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65584-0_9
- Lewin K. (1935). *A dynamic theory of personality: Selected papers*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Lewis, S. C. (2020). The objects and objectives of journalism research during the coronavirus pandemic and beyond. *Digital Journalism*, 8(5), 681-689.
- Liao, H. & Hitchcock, J. (2018). Reported credibility techniques in higher education evaluation studies that use qualitative methods: A research synthesis. National Library of Medicine. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29602062/>
- Mannion, J. (2022). Promoting independence through project-based learning. My College. Retrieved June 17, 2024, from <https://my.chartered.college/research-hub/promoting-independence-through-project-based-learning/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CM>
- Metykova, M. & Císařová, L. (2023). *Peripheral News Workers' Autonomy: The Case of a Czech Regional Television Newsroom*. Taylor & Francis Online
- Moon, M. C. (2019). Triangulation: A Method to Increase Validity, Reliability, and Legitimation in Clinical Research. *Journal of Emergency Nursing*, 45(1), 103–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2018.11.004>
- Moore, K. (2023). The Profound Influence of Teachers that Shape Students' Lives. (n.d.). [www.linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/profound-influence-teachers-shape-students-lives-dr-kim-moore?fbclid=Iw). Retrieved June 17, 2024, from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/profound-influence-teachers-shape-students-lives-dr-kim-moore?fbclid=Iw>
- Morales, S. (2022) *School Resource Management: Building a stronger system*. (2022). https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/62c43c708fa8f54e8fb7db8a/SRM_Building_a_stronger_system_strategy.pdf?fbclid
- Moreno, J. (2019). *The Student Journalist and Student Media Adviser Perspective of Censorship in Student Media at Public Universities across the United States*. ProQuest
- Morgan, R. (2020). *The Charger: A Case Study Of Leadership Decisions And The Oxford High School Student Newspaper*. Electronic Theses and Dissertations. <https://egrove.olemiss.edu/etd/1858/>
- Mullings, C. (2023). Developing independent learning skills that improve outcomes. (n.d.). [Blog.irisconnect.com](https://blog.irisconnect.com). Retrieved June 17, 2024, from <https://blog.irisconnect.com/uk/blog/9-tips-for-encouraging-students-to-become-independent-learners/?fbclid>
- Nassaji, H. (2020). Good Qualitative Research. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(4), 427-431. doi:10.1177/1362168820941288
- Natividad, A. & Gapasin, A. (2021). Public School Paper Advisers' Assessment on the Implementation of Campus Journalism Act in the Philippines. 8th International Conference Research on Behavioral and social Sciences.
- Nnebedum, Chidi & Egboka, Patience & Ndidi,. (2018). Analysis of Resource Management Strategies Adopted by Principals for Secondary Schools Improvement in Enugu State, Nigeria. *International Journal Of Advance Research And Innovative Ideas In Education*. 3.
- Obagwu, P. & Idris, K. (2019). Social Responsibility Theory of the Press: A Critique of Its Application and Constraints. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT*
- Paguirigan, Marjorie Janel & Paguirigan, Edmar M.. (2023). *SCHOOLS PRESS CONFERENCE COACHES: THEIR LIVED EXPERIENCES*. 25. 1-16
- Piaget, J. (1973). *To Understand is to Invent: The Future of Education*. New York: Viking Press.
- Prakash, S., & Xavier, S. A. (2020). A Study on Attitude of Urban And Rural College Student Teachers Towards Science. *I-Manager's Journal on Educational Psychology*, 7(3), 13–17. <https://doi.org/10.26634/jpsy.7.3.2529>
- Rai, N. (2016, August 29). A study on purposive sampling method in research. [Academia.edu](https://www.academia.edu).
- Rafiq, Shahid & Kamran, Farrukh. (2022). Impact of School Environment on Students' Academic Achievements at the University Level. *VFAST Transactions on Education and Social Sciences*. 10. 19-30.
- Ranieri, Maria & Nardi, Andrea & Fabbro, Francesco. (2019). Teachers' Professional Development on Media and Intercultural Education. Results from some participatory research in Europe. *Research on Education and Media*. 11. 110-120. [10.2478/rem-2019-0015](https://doi.org/10.2478/rem-2019-0015).

- Rashid, Y., Rashid, A., Warraich, M. S., Sabir, S., & Waseem, A. (2019). Case Study Method: A Step-by-Step Guide for Business Researchers. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919862424>
- Ratminingsih, N. M., Marhaeni, A. A. I. N., & Vigayanti, L. P. D. (2018). Self-Assessment: The Effect on Students' Independence and Writing Competence. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(3), 277–290. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1183438>
- Reinjoe F. Namit, J., D. Parico, A., & C. Magno, J. (2022). Paperless Publication: Surveying the Shifting Shape of Campus Journalism. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences: Proceedings*, 11(4(s)), pp. 408–419. https://european-science.com/eojnss_proc/article/view/6725
- Saad, Sh & Al-Ajmy, & Al-Mutairi, Musaed. (2024). The Impact and Future of Student's Independent Learning. *MECCA Journal of Middle European Construction and Design of Cars*. 68.
- Schrøder, K. C. (2019, February 14). What Do News Readers Really Want to Read About? How Relevance Works for News Audiences. Reuters Institute Digital News Report. <https://www.digitalnewsreport.org/publications/2019/news-readers-really-want-read-relevance>
- Siebert, F., Peterson, T., & Schramm, W. (1956). *Four theories of the press: The authoritarian, libertarian, social responsibility, and Soviet communist concepts of what the press should be and do*. Urbana: University of Illinois.
- Sutton, J., & Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative research: data collection, analysis, and management. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*, 68(3), 226-231. <https://doi.org/10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456>
- Tremblay, A. M., & Cadieux, E. (2018). A reflection on the challenge of protecting confidentiality of participants while disseminating research results locally. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-018-0279-0>
- Valeza, A., Pedrito, J., Bermudo, & Yango, A. (2021). Express Or Suppress: School Administrators' understanding Of Campus Journalists' freedom Of Expression. *International Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences Studies*, 6, 2582–1601. <https://ijahss.com/Paper/06052021/1179451422.pdf>
- Vogts, T. (2018). EFFECTS OF JOURNALISM EDUCATION ON STUDENT ENGAGEMENT: A CASE STUDY OF A SMALL-TOWN SCHOLASTIC PRESS PROGRAM. (2018). <https://mospace.umsystem.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10355/66290/research.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y&fbclid=IwZXh0bgNh>
- Wang, Q., Hou, H. & Li, Z. (2022). Participative Leadership: A Literature Review and Prospects for Future Research. *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Ward, R. (2023). The Impact of Positive Recognition on Student Performance. (n.d.). [Pathwaylabs.io](https://pathwaylabs.io/blog/the-impact-of-positive-recognition-on-student-performance#:~:text=Positive%20recognition%20serves%20as%20a%20bridge%20that%20strengthens%20the%20bond). Retrieved June 18, 2024, from <https://pathwaylabs.io/blog/the-impact-of-positive-recognition-on-student-performance#:~:text=Positive%20recognition%20serves%20as%20a%20bridge%20that%20strengthens%20the%20bond>

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